

Branding of Hainan 海南品牌塑造

Hainan, Naturally Yours

White Paper research conducted by the Student Entrepreneurship & Innovation Center(SEIC) at Hainan University-Arizona State University International College (HAIC)

HSEIC

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This research was conducted by professors and students at Hainan University-ASU International College in Hainan as a practical research project without any support from outside groups. Analysis, ideas, and conclusions in this report are strictly the responsibility of the authors of this report.

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Branding of Hainan

1. Introduction

The entire island of Hainan has now fully launched its Free Trade Port status as of December 2025 (China Daily, 2025). It is now entering a new phase of development. More open, more global, more complex, more innovative, and more prosperous are some of the opportunities and challenges Hainan will face in the coming years. In this paper, we focus on one aspect of Hainan's development needs: how should Hainan brand itself? This is, by definition, a vast topic and has significant strategic implications for the province. Proper branding will act to introduce Hainan to the rest of the world, the way we want to define ourselves. Branding Hainan will enable strategic control over the island's introduction to the international community. Hainan's brand will help convey a clear, unique message and spark interest in the island. With so many places around the world competing for attention in the noisy global marketplace, branding Hainan is a necessary step to strategically position the island in the minds of international consumers and businesses.

Branding, by definition, is a very long-term project. Many businesses and destinations invest significant resources in promoting their brands. Successful branding requires a consistent and well-developed plan with supporting analysis. The plan's execution requires a budget and a purposeful and holistic strategy to maintain and further enhance the brand. A successful branding project requires time, money, and commitment.

For example, it is widely known that the global tourism industry is highly competitive. With very few "unique" destinations, many are now adopting marketing-driven, price-based strategies to compete and attract international travellers and businesses. Many destinations are not focusing on sustainability or unique experiences. They focus on total arrivals as a measure of success (Jose Luis Ruiz-Real, 2020). To assess competitiveness based on a destination's physical attributes, we analysed and compared international tropical destinations in Southeast Asia. One conclusion is that it will be tough to create a unique brand that focuses on Hainan's location and the "tropical" appeal as its primary selling point.

Also, we focus not only on the primary branding effort but also on secondary and tertiary branding. The depth of Hainan's overall branding strategy will go beyond simply sending the right message to people outside Hainan. It can also help Hainan organize its development efforts. This is a complex project. However, it can institutionalize the development strategy and path forward, optimal resource allocation, and socially attentive development, while preserving what is uniquely Hainan. With the right branding plan, the classic formula and logic of sacrificing our long-term assets for near-term economic development gains can be avoided.

Upon analysing the unique aspects of Hainan and incorporating the development objectives stated by the leaders of China and Hainan, we conclude that "Hainan, Naturally Yours" should be the primary branding slogan that best captures Hainan. The secondary branding will highlight two distinct aspects of Hainan: its unique, untouched nature and business opportunities. They are "Experience Nature" and "Your Gateway to & from China". Using these primary and secondary branding concepts, we have researched and developed a comprehensive study on how to implement these plans, along with detailed project recommendations for specific projects.

The spirit behind Hainan's development path, as reflected in its nascent FTP initiative, is to create new opportunities rather than compete for global market share. In this light, we recommend that the overall branding of Hainan focus on building on its strengths and assets as the core foundation to

usher in innovative and new ways for Hainan to create economic prosperity and stability. The leading brand, “Hainan, Naturally Yours,” and the sub-brands, “Experience Nature” and “Your Gateway to and from China,” accomplish these key objectives.

2. Why Branding is Important?

We encounter advertisements for many products, services, companies, and destinations every day. Some we remember and some we delete from our memory. Also, even with a similar value, we sometimes pay more for specific products. What causes these types of behavior to remember and pay a premium for goods and services? It is due to the connection to the products and services, and how they make us feel about them (Sheikh Farhan Ashraf, 2017). In fact, with similar functionality, some well-branded smartphone companies report operating margins of 20%-30%. In a highly competitive technology product industry, this additional margin can significantly raise the company’s valuation in the marketplace. (SEC Database). For this reason, many companies invest significant effort and resources in establishing and promoting their brands.

Destinations are also investing resources to brand themselves to capture the interests of global travellers. In 2024, the total global travel market size was \$11.5 trillion (World Tourism Market, 2024). In terms of economic size ranking, the international travel market would be the third-largest in the world, roughly three times the size of Japan or Germany (World Bank 2024). To establish its position in this large market, many destinations are branding themselves. Some are using a very logical approach to highlight their character to draw the attention of the travellers. For example, words like pyramid, aurora, Polynesian, and Great Wall show links to the locations without even mentioning them. These are prominent examples of strong place branding—where a single word or image can be associated with a location. However, many destinations face the challenge of building a brand without clear, unique attributes.

Destination branding is a well-researched topic, as many locations seek the right formula to compete for global market share. One clear conclusion is that there are many ways to brand a destination, but many branding efforts lack a unique physical character. Some use emotional triggers to brand destinations (Jose Luis Ruiz-Real, 2020).

Figure 1 Tourism Promotion Banners

Source: Various Official Tourism Boards

The challenge Hainan faces in this over-crowded destination branding is how to truly capture the unique aspects of Hainan and communicate them clearly to the global marketplace. The first step is to identify Hainan’s unique attributes that can truly capture international travellers' attention. Then accurately combine these attributes to represent Hainan's attractions. One immediate challenge is the divergent character of the main unique attributes—a tropical island with a Free Trade Port mandate. Hainan's branding needs to combine images of coconut trees and busy ports into a cohesive message for global travellers and businesses. Moreover, branding that does not deliver on its promises will not be successful. If a destination promotes snow as its main attraction but lacks

any, it will not attract repeat visitors and will face negative publicity. This has more significant implications for Hainan. To brand Hainan effectively, many parts of Hainan will need to move together to support the new brand strategy. This can make implementing the new branding strategy more complex, but in the long run, it can help Hainan better prepare for the challenges and opportunities.

3. Trends in Tropical Destination Branding in Southeast Asia

3.1. Comparative Study on Four Southeast Asia Destinations

Hainan is located in the middle of a diverse tropical destination in Southeast Asia (see Figure 2). Hainan is embedded in a highly competitive regional tourism environment alongside well-established tropical destinations such as Cebu, Philippines; Bali, Indonesia; Phuket, Thailand; and Da Nang, Vietnam. These destinations have evolved over several decades into globally recognised tourism hubs, supported by strong destination branding, diversified tourism portfolios, and relatively mature governance and marketing frameworks. Their development trajectories illustrate how coastal and island destinations in Southeast Asia have leveraged natural assets, cultural appeal, and international connectivity to achieve sustained tourism growth.

Figure 2: Map of the South China Sea and neighboring countries.

Source: Encyclopaedia Britannica, Inc.

Situating Hainan within this comparative regional context provides an essential analytical baseline for assessing its own tourism development and branding strategies. While Hainan shares similar environmental characteristics and market aspirations, it operates under distinct institutional, policy, and domestic market conditions, as well as a new government-led initiative to establish a Free Trade

Port in Hainan. A comparative perspective, therefore, enables a more nuanced understanding of Hainan’s positioning and opportunities. We compared international tourist data across these destinations to establish a reference point for Hainan.

Figure 3 International Visitors, 2024 (millions)

Source: Haikou General Station of Immigration, Badan Pusat Statistik Provinsi Bali, Sugbo News, Phuket Immigration Office, Da Nang Statistical Office

As Figure 3 shows, the number of foreign visitors to other popular Southeast Asian tropical destinations is much larger. They are much more mature destinations with a long history of attracting foreign visitors. Hainan will face a difficult time competing solely based on the “Tropical” concept against these established locations.

Figure 4: Average per Foreign Tourist Spending, 2024

Source: Vietnam General Statistics Office, Central Statistics Agency of Indonesia, Bank of Thailand, the Philippines Government

Figure 4 illustrates that spending per foreign visitor is comparable across popular Southeast Asian destinations in 2024. This data is closely monitored in each destination as a barometer of foreign visitor consumption behavior (KPMG, 2025). These numbers are somewhat steady, with slight fluctuation, as there are no dramatic policy changes. Any meaningful changes occur when these destinations open their visa policies to allow for easier access. Competition to attract foreign visitors is intensifying in the region. Hainan data on foreign traveller spending was challenging to obtain. According to a KPMG study, the average spending by a foreign traveller to Hainan is about twice that of a Chinese visitor. Also, two dramatic policy changes will impact spending and visitor patterns as the complete conversion of Free Trade Port status across the island takes effect.

Also, here are samples of how each of these destinations is branding its appeal to the global marketplace (see Figure 5).

Figure 5: Destinations' branding

Source: Various Official Tourism Boards

3.2. The "Tropical" is a Saturated Concept

In this context, positioning Hainan primarily as a generic "tropical" destination presents strategic limitations, as the tropical tourism imaginary in Southeast Asia is already densely populated by long-established and globally recognisable brands. Destinations such as Bali, Phuket, and Cebu have consolidated strong emotional narratives and visual identities around shared climatic and coastal attributes, making differentiation based on "tropicality" alone increasingly ineffective (see Figure 6). For Hainan, this saturation underscores the need to move beyond conventional tropical branding towards more distinctive value propositions grounded in its unique policy framework, cultural landscapes, and developmental trajectory. For Hainan to leave a strong first impression on travellers and businesses outside, the branding built around "tropical" will not convey the proper, unique message; hence, Hainan's branding must have a different focus.

Figure 6: Promotional Pictures from Bali, Phuket, Cebu, Da Nang

Source: Various Official Tourism Boards

3.3. Popular Domestic Destinations in China

Comparing other popular destinations within China, we see many of them branding around a physical tourist location. These iconic destinations are synonymous with images of China in the minds of people outside China. To draw their interest and attention, these strong brands of other Chinese destinations pose a big challenge for Hainan. How can Hainan position itself against the Great Wall and the Terracotta Army in China? It should not. Also, with the full activation of Hainan FTP, it is no longer just a vacation destination. This makes it more difficult for Hainan to develop a unique brand.

Figure 7: Annual Tourist Visits

Source: Various Local Government Agencies

Official Slogans	
Great Wall	Great Wall Hero
The Forbidden City	Explore the World with Us
Xi'an	Capital of Tang Poetry
Shanghai	This is Shanghai

Figure 8: Official Tourism Slogans of Various Attractions and Top Tourist Cities in China

Source: Various Local Government Agencies

3.4. Unique Qualities of Hainan

3.4.1. Untouched Nature

Hainan is a tropical island. However, compared to other well-established tropical destinations, the number of visitors and the development of typical infrastructure, driven by sheer capacity, are lagging. Some would propose that Hainan needs to build more resorts and infrastructure to compete. We disagree. Ironically, the best asset of Hainan is the underdeveloped nature and way of life in remote villages. This is Hainan's unique asset—untouched nature.

Some of the assets of Hainan include: a small fishing village with pristine, untouched beaches; tropical fruit farms where simple farming still exists; a rain forest with nature's design still intact; and various traditional villages (volcanic villages, Li and Mao ethnic villages) where the way of life is still

preserved. The untouched nature and the simple way of life still exist in Hainan. This should be one of Hainan’s branding pillars.

In addition, Hainan is home to the Hainan Tropical Rainforest National Park, China’s first national park in a tropical rainforest setting, which protects some of the country’s highest levels of biodiversity and endemic species. This national park framework provides Hainan with a rare opportunity to align destination branding with conservation-led development, ecological stewardship, well-being tourism, and other low-impact tourism models. Unlike mass-oriented resort destinations, Hainan can position itself as a living landscape where nature protection, cultural continuity, and community-based livelihoods remain central. These qualities offer a strong foundation for a differentiated branding strategy that emphasises authenticity, ecological integrity, and long-term sustainability rather than scale and volume.

In parallel, Hainan is emerging as an essential hub for sports tourism, hosting a growing portfolio of international and national events in surfing, cycling, sailing, running, and endurance sports. The island’s natural conditions, such as coastlines, mountains, forests, and year-round warm climate, allow sport and outdoor recreation to be embedded within largely unspoiled landscapes rather than in purpose-built mega-facilities. This creates opportunities to integrate sports tourism with conservation, wellness, and slow tourism narratives, reinforcing Hainan’s positioning as an active yet nature-oriented destination. When aligned with its national park system and rural communities, sports tourism can further strengthen Hainan’s distinct identity beyond conventional tropical resort models.

3.4.2. Hainan Free Trade Port (FTP)

Another unique aspect of Hainan is that China has designated the entire province as the newest Free Trade Port. As we enter the maturing phase of China’s export- and manufacturing-based growth era, the Hainan FTP’s mandate is to “Build the Hainan FTP with high standards aimed at advancing high-quality development of Hainan and contributing to forging a new development paradigm nationwide” (China Daily, 2025). This is a big task- Hainan FTP to find a new development pathway for China. Challenging, but it is another unique attribute that is very important to Hainan’s branding.

The challenge is to incorporate these two unrelated concepts into a single branding plan. In a way, the two unique attributes are not just different but have “opposite” implications, as the image of nature with trees and clean beaches collides with that of FTP with busy ports and factories. Hainan’s branding must capture the essence of these two unique factors into a single concept.

Figure 9: Stock Photos of a beach near Sanya and Haikou Port

Source: beach-on-map.com, alarmy.com

3.5. Branding for Emotional Response

Too many branding plans focus on a physical location and descriptive words to support it. This triggers image-based responses from the recipients. We focused on the emotional response trigger for the Hainan branding. Selecting the words for branding not as a description but as a purposeful emotion trigger to convey a feeling rather than an image (Rovika Prem, 2025). This is the best path to combine the two key assets of Hainan that are very different—nature and FTP.

There are two reasons for this approach. Hainan branding has to be different than others. Hainan needs a non-traditional branding strategy to promote its unique assets. In the era of too much video stimulation, the retention of a video message is very short. There is no lasting impact from the image-based message. Also, this approach, which focuses on an emotional trigger, aligns with the message Hainan seeks to convey to the recipients. It indicates that Hainan is different. A successful branding project for Hainan should deliver a positive, differentiated message and ultimately trigger a potential action.

4. Introducing the “Hainan, Naturally Yours” Brand for Hainan

Figure 10: Hainan, Naturally Yours

Source: authors' figure

4.1. The Primary Branding Slogan

By combining “Hainan” and “Naturally Yours”, this branding slogan is triggering multiple layers of emotional responses. The first layer is very straightforward. Hainan is nature, and Hainan is yours. Both are inviting suggestions. Instead of saying directly that we are great, the branding slogan suggests that the whole of Hainan is for you to experience. The “naturally” part highlights untouched nature, simple traditional villages, and clean air. The “yours” part highlights the benefits of Hainan FTP and conveys a personal experience.

4.2. Informal Survey of Foreign Faculty

To assess the effectiveness of this slogan, we conducted an informal questionnaire of international faculty at our college. We collected 33 responses from the 40 questionnaire invitations. Figure 11 illustrates the survey results.

Figure 11: Foreign Faculty Survey Results

Source: authors of this research report

Based on the survey responses, the slogan "Hainan, Naturally Yours" elicits mixed but predominantly positive reactions, with curiosity (30.3%) and interest (24.2%) being the most common initial responses. The phrase "Naturally Yours" is most strongly associated with Hainan's natural environment (36.4%) and a sense of belonging (33.3%), indicating effective conveyance of both ecological and emotional appeals. Respondents clearly perceive the intended dual message, with strong majorities recognizing implications of both "Hainan is Yours" (75.8% combined strongly/somewhat see) and "Hainan is Nature" (81.8% combined). Overall, the slogan is rated

favourably, with 57.6% evaluating it as "good" or "very good." However, a notable portion (21.2%) remains neutral or negative, suggesting room for refinement in messaging clarity or resonance.

The qualitative feedback provides nuanced insight into the slogan's reception. While some respondents found it sounded like a generic marketing slogan or was non-intuitive, these responses underscore the importance of supporting the slogan with a distinctive visual identity and tangible actions to avoid perceptions of cliché. Conversely, other participants explicitly noted a sense of inclusivity and belonging, directly affirming the intended emotional resonance of "Yours." Additionally, the interpretation of the slogan as both an invitation to explore Hainan's natural environment and a reference to the environment itself confirms its successful dual-layered messaging. Overall, these mixed reactions highlight that while the slogan effectively plants an engaging conceptual seed, its full impact will depend on consistent and authentic implementation across all touchpoints.

From a branding perspective, the survey results suggest that "Hainan, Naturally Yours" provides a solid strategic foundation but cannot serve as a compelling standalone message. Its strength lies in the successful coupling of nature-based and emotional narratives, which aligns well with Hainan's long-term positioning as a distinctive, restorative destination. However, the presence of neutral and critical responses indicates that the slogan requires careful activation through coherent storytelling, place-specific visuals, and demonstrable alignment with policy and products to avoid perceptions of generic branding. Strategically, this implies that Hainan's branding efforts should focus less on slogan innovation and more on translating the promise of "Naturally Yours" into concrete immersive experiences, governance practices, and on-the-ground transformations that make the brand credible and differentiated.

5. The Secondary Branding Slogans

As mentioned earlier, Hainan's unique appeal has two diverging characteristics. One is the untouched nature, and the other is a Free Trade Port initiative, which represents a new economic development path for China. In the secondary branding effort, there are two slogans to identify the two diverging assets of Hainan's appeal.

5.1. Untouched Nature and Simple Life

"Experience Nature" ties into the primary slogan via "Naturally" wording. This emphasis on nature can encompass the types of branding and experiences Hainan can offer to visitors. Experiencing the simple life of a remote fishing village, a volcanic village, traditional life in the ethnic villages, and the tranquillity of untouched tropical rain forest. These are the unique experiences Hainan can offer visitors looking for less-crowded, relaxing vacation destinations. While nature-based tourism itself is not a novel concept, its relevance and demand have intensified significantly in the post-pandemic context, as travellers increasingly seek restorative, low-density environments that support physical, mental, and emotional well-being (Buckley & Westaway, 2020; Ma, et al., 2021). Experiences rooted in tranquillity, simplicity, and connection to nature respond to a broader shift towards wellness, slow travel, and meaningful engagement with place. Within this context, Hainan's relatively intact natural and cultural landscapes position it well to meet emerging market expectations. Framing "Experience Nature" around restoration, resilience, and well-being strengthens its strategic relevance while aligning with long-term sustainability objectives. In parallel, China's younger generations are showing rapidly growing interest in nature- and outdoor-oriented travel, including trekking, hiking, camping, glamping, surfing, and campervan tourism (Hu, et al., 2025; Lu, et al., 2022; Wengel, et al.

2022; Wengel, et al., 2024), reflecting changing lifestyle values and a desire for freedom, immersion, and nature-based experiences. We further developed this concept in more detail in the later section.

5.1.1. Remedy for the Urban Stress

The intensification of urban life has given rise to a complex form of stress, shaped by environmental congestion, social pressure, economic competition, digital saturation, and an accelerating pace of everyday life. For many urban residents, leisure travel no longer functions as genuine recovery, as holidays often replicate the same speed, stimulation, and performance-oriented behaviours found in cities. This phenomenon, frequently described as the need for “a vacation from a vacation,” highlights a growing disconnect between travel and restoration. Within this context, Hainan has the potential to position itself as a landscape of slowing down, simplicity, and reconnection. Rather than framing nature narrowly through a tropical lens, Hainan’s value lies in its diverse natural environments, including rainforests, coastal ecosystems, agricultural landscapes, volcanic terrain, and protected national park areas. These spaces enable visitors to step out of urban rhythms and re-engage with natural cycles, sensory experiences, and everyday forms that prioritise presence over productivity.

Slow travel practices are central to this positioning. Extended stays in rural villages, participation in small-scale agricultural activities like fruit picking, low-intensity outdoor recreation like hiking, and engagement with local cultural practices encourage deeper, less extractive forms of tourism. Such experiences allow visitors to detach from constant digital connectivity, reduce cognitive overload, and experience a form of “detox” from urban stressors. In this sense, simplicity itself becomes a tourism asset, offering time, quiet, and unstructured experiences that are increasingly scarce in urban settings.

Outdoor and sports-based activities further reinforce this restorative potential. Hiking, trekking, cycling, surfing, paddling, camping/glamping, and other nature-based activities support physical well-being while simultaneously fostering mental clarity, emotional regulation, and embodied connection to place. When embedded within natural and rural landscapes rather than commercialised resort environments, these activities contribute to holistic well-being without reinforcing high-consumption or high-pressure tourism models, while also supporting the local economy sustainably.

Cultural and rural tourism also play a critical role in this restorative framework. Encounters with traditional villages, fishing communities, and ethnic minority cultures offer alternative perspectives on time, social relations, and human–nature interactions. These experiences support reflection, cultural learning, and emotional grounding, while generating sustainable economic opportunities for remote communities. Collectively, nature-based, slow, and culturally embedded tourism positions Hainan as a destination not just for escape, but for renewal, rebalancing, and long-term well-being in response to the stresses of contemporary urban life.

5.2. Hainan: The Gateway to and from China

“Your Gateway to & from China” is another secondary branding slogan that captures the opportunities Hainan offers to businesses and investors outside the province. As Chinese leaders have noted, the implementation of the Hainan FTP has national implications. As such, the true appeal of Hainan can be fully described only when it becomes a gateway to and from China. In many developing countries, the only direction of foreign goods and investment is considered to be inbound—money and people. The true benefit of Hainan FTP is the two-way flows of goods and money, with Hainan as the hub for these activities. By incorporating the concept of “in and out” into

the slogan, we are highlighting Hainan's proper two-way role. With the Hainan FTP now in place, it is an ideal location for foreign businesses and investors to establish a presence to access China. Also, foreign and domestic companies can use Hainan as an outbound gateway to bring China to the outside world. One desired initial response to this slogan is “Why and How?” This trigger would be great, as it would show intellectual engagement. There has to be an easy, comprehensive information-delivery infrastructure to support this branding slogan.

Figure 12: Three Tiers of Hainan Branding Slogan

Source: authors of this research report

5.2.1. Access to Nature with Modern Conveniences

Working alongside the Hainan Free Trade Port initiative, Hainan can be described as a destination that uniquely integrates access to high-quality natural environments with the reliability and comfort of modern urban systems. The FTP framework has accelerated investments in transport infrastructure, digital connectivity, healthcare, logistics, and international-standard services, reducing many of the barriers traditionally associated with nature- and rural-based tourism. As a result, visitors can move efficiently between airports, cities, villages, coastlines, and protected areas, enabling flexible travel patterns that combine immersion in nature with contemporary standards of convenience and safety. This hybrid positioning is particularly significant in the context of post-pandemic travel preferences, where accessibility, health security, and predictability have become central factors in decision-making. Hainan allows travellers to engage in slow travel, outdoor recreation, and cultural encounters without the risks or logistical challenges often linked to remote destinations. Short travel distances, high-quality accommodation options across different price segments, and reliable digital services support longer stays, remote work, and extended nature-based experiences. This makes Hainan especially attractive to urban residents seeking restorative travel without disengaging entirely from professional or family responsibilities.

From a strategic perspective, the coexistence of modern conveniences and natural accessibility enables Hainan to develop a distinctive nature+ tourism model. Visitors can experience forests, rural villages, coastal landscapes, and national parks during the day, while retaining access to healthcare, transport, and urban amenities when needed. This reduces the psychological and practical costs of

choosing nature-based travel and broadens the potential market beyond adventure-oriented or highly mobile tourists.

Importantly, this model also supports sustainability objectives. Concentrating modern infrastructure in existing urban nodes while facilitating controlled access to surrounding natural and rural areas can help prevent overdevelopment of sensitive landscapes. When aligned with zoning, visitor management, and community-based tourism frameworks, the Free Trade Port initiative can thus function as an enabler of balanced development. In this sense, Hainan is positioned not as a trade-off between nature and modernity, but as a destination where the two reinforce one another, offering a credible pathway for nature-led, well-being-oriented tourism in a contemporary economic context.

Another unique aspect of Hainan is easy accessibility to untouched natural locations. All the nature areas and traditional simple life destinations in Hainan are easily accessible from a high-speed rail station or a major highway. Also, Haikou is a unique city where “tropical urbanism” can be applied. It has modern infrastructure comparable to major cities, with convenient access to untouched nature. A place where one can work in a globally competitive company setting while enjoying the benefits of the pristine nature in a tropical setting. It is an excellent incentive for anyone or any company who wants to benefit from working at the “gateway to & from China”.

6. Defining and conceptualizing Nature+ Tourism

Hainan’s traditional focus on 3S tourism—sun, sea, and sand—has boosted its economic development and increased its profile in specific tourist markets (Ferreira et al., 2024). However, this focus could now limit the island’s potential to attain wider international recognition, as envisioned by both public and private stakeholders. To stand out beyond the “Hawaii of the East”, it is crucial to diversify and adapt to address regional competition, evolving visitor expectations, and environmental challenges.

Fortunately, Hainan benefits from a diverse range of natural, built, and cultural assets that, when integrated thoughtfully, can establish a unique competitive advantage difficult for competitors to replicate. In this approach to product diversification, the “nature” component continues to be central to the tourism offering. However, we also elevate the rural mountainous interior from the periphery of the island’s tourism scene, giving it equal importance alongside the coastal regions.

6.1. Hainan should develop Nature+ Tourism

We recommend that Hainan develop a cohesive, multi-layered tourism landscape that integrates the sea and rainforest, encompassing wellness, tropical agriscapes, Nanyang heritage, ethnic traditions, ecological initiatives, tea and coffee culture, and modern leisure activities. These elements should support each other to create a unique Nature+ Tourism product. In this way, the diversification will strengthen Hainan's brand rather than dilute it. This strategy will help transform Hainan from a mere beach destination into a diverse, multifaceted place to explore, while still maintaining a strong, recognizable identity.

This market need, which is driven by a growing desire for authentic local experiences beyond conventional tourism offerings, has long been recognized by academics. However, only recently has the visitor economy begun to acknowledge it and allocate resources, often after prestigious consulting firms endorsed it. Accordingly, industry reports from major consulting firms such as Destinations International (2019) and JLL (2018) consistently highlight that consumers increasingly

seek unique and authentic travel experiences. This trend has become a top priority for destinations worldwide, and Hainan risks falling behind if the focus remains solely on the all-inclusive 3S model.

6.2. Nature+ Tourism: Revitalization of Rural Hainan

Nature+ Tourism on Hainan Island (see Figure 13) is thus a hybrid tourism product that promotes eco-wellness for visitors while actively supporting the revitalization of underdeveloped rural areas. It goes beyond traditional nature tourism by including human-shaped spaces such as charming ethnic and volcanic villages and farmscapes, and by integrating intangible cultural heritage elements of Nanyang culture and the Li and Miao ethnic groups. It embodies the principles of slow travel, encouraging tourists to go beyond mere consumption of landscapes by emphasizing local people as key figures in the destination. This contrasts with the fast-paced, often superficial experiences of conventional mass tourism by encouraging tourists to take their time, savor the journey, and engage deeply with the places they visit. This means avoiding the consumption-driven mindset that often characterizes modern travel and instead valuing the local culture, people, and ecosystems as central protagonists of the destination. Slow travel (Dickinson, 2015) fosters mindfulness and presence, allowing tourists to truly appreciate the beauty and richness of Hainan Island.

Figure 13: Nature+ Tourism products (yellow), and development and management models (green)

Source: authors of this research report

In this vein, ecowellness (Reese & Myers, 2012) is a holistic framework that integrates physical, mental, and spiritual well-being through immersive and sustainable experiences in nature. It is achieved by engaging tourists in activities that not only rejuvenate their bodies but also nourish their spirits and minds. This could include hiking through the lush Diaoluo Shan rainforest near Sanya, exploring ancient volcanic landscapes in Rongtan Village near Haikou (Cimino et al., 2025), and participating in local cultural festivals that celebrate Hainan’s diverse ethnic communities. The goal is to foster a deep connection between tourists and the island’s natural and cultural landscapes, promoting stewardship and appreciation for its unique resources.

6.3. Regenerative Tourism: Enhancing the Health of Destinations

The concept of regenerative tourism plays a pivotal role in shaping Nature+ Tourism. Regenerative tourism (Bellato et al., 2023) seeks to restore and enhance the health of destinations, focusing on the well-being of both the environment and local populations. On Hainan Island, this means implementing practices that not only minimize ecological footprints but also actively contribute to the revitalization of rural areas. This includes supporting local businesses, investing in sustainable infrastructure, and promoting biodiversity conservation. By adopting regenerative principles, Nature+ Tourism aims to create a positive impact on both the environment and local communities, ensuring that the benefits of tourism are distributed equitably. Also on the regenerative front, permatourism (Ferreira et al., 2021) draws on permaculture principles to inform the design of eco-friendly accommodations (e.g., principle 6, use and value local resources), sustainable food systems (e.g., principle 7, design from patterns to details), and community-based initiatives (e.g., integrate rather than segregate). These principles emphasize working with existing processes rather than against them to create resilient and harmonious environments. Significantly, regenerative tourism practices not only minimize environmental impact but also actively contribute to the revitalization of natural and human-shaped landscapes.

6.4. Rural Communities are vital to Hainan's Unique Branding

Critically, rural communities play a vital role in our vision for Hainan's Nature+ Tourism. Visitors' hunger for authenticity cannot be satisfied by the staged theatricals of conventional tourism (Morais et al., 2017), and it opens the door for home-grown micro-entrepreneurship to close that gap (KC et al., 2021). While the range of business opportunities is broad, the easiest to develop is the accommodation sector, which includes homestays, hostels, and small boutique hotels to cater to different preferences and budgets. It goes without saying that, in our vision, the accommodations in these locations will be owned and operated by the villages, with the economic benefits directly supporting local communities and preventing economic leakage to the corporate sector.

In conclusion, Nature+ Tourism represents a forward-thinking, sustainable approach to tourism that seeks to achieve ecowellness for tourists while revitalizing rural areas. By embracing the principles of regenerative tourism and permatourism, Nature+ Tourism transcends conventional nature tourism, incorporating human-shaped spaces and promoting slow travel that values local communities as protagonists. This holistic, sustainable model of tourism has the potential to set a new standard for responsible, enriching travel experiences on Hainan Island.

Text Box 1: Tropical Urbanism

Tropical Urbanism is a well-researched topic. The global trend of urbanization has now spread to tropical areas, raising concerns about sustainability. Many institutions, such as the UN, have done extensive research on this topic (UN, 2015). In this section, we focus on two specific issues related to Hainan: the balance between tropical and urban environments, and how this balance can be incorporated into Hainan's overall branding effort.

Haikou is the most populous city in Hainan (3 million people), followed by Sanya (1 million people). Then there are several cities with populations under 500,000. By Chinese standards, the urban centers in Hainan are smaller. One way to economically grow is to increase the size of the urban centers in Hainan. This direction can be highly damaging to Hainan's core asset—the island's pristine environment.

The challenge for Hainan, as it becomes more international and developed, is balancing tropical nature and urban life. The word it chooses as the primary objective will determine the “success” of urbanization while maintaining what is naturally endowed in Hainan. One of Hainan's best assets is its clean environment. It has to be preserved and sustained. If ignored, Hainan's future will be just like that of other tropical locations overrun by urbanization. There are many examples of megacities around the world that have ignored this balance. Even in neighboring Southeast Asia, a shift in balance is underway (AQI, 2024).

Figure 14: 2024 Average Air Quality Index

Source: AQI World Wide Air Quality Report 2024

There is a notion that taller buildings, more people, and more traffic jams will define the success of urbanism and invite internationalization; furthermore, that the air and noise pollution are a necessary sacrifice for urbanization and the economic prosperity it brings. The formula and path for any ambitious urban center to become more international. What if Hainan adopted conservation and sustainability as its primary development objectives and focused on improving the quality of life (not quantity) to become more international? Health care, leisure, legal and financial services, and education are all essential daily services that the urban population needs, whether local or foreign. By making these daily needs more readily available for foreigners, the international talent attraction and tropical urbanism goals can be met. Hainan should adopt conservation, sustainability, and improvement in quality of life as the main criteria for its urbanization framework. This is consistent with directives from China's leadership, which recently defined one of Hainan's key mandates as "a national pilot zone for ecological conservation" (China Daily, 2025). Hainan can offer a new tropical urbanism — where you can work in a globally competitive environment that has convenient services and go windsurfing in the blue ocean during your lunch break: tropical urbanism, Hainan style.

7. Implementation of the Branding Campaign

There are five simple, logical rules to follow when implementing a significant new initiative, such as a Branding campaign for Hainan.

- 1) Every action needs to be purposeful and consistent.

- 2) A comprehensive education and “buy-in” from all parties that are involved. No lagging parts, as they will limit effectiveness and ultimate success. This encompasses both the private and public sectors.
- 3) Focus on communicating the message clearly, and focus on the recipient’s comprehension as the rule for effective communication.
- 4) Build awareness in Hainan.
- 5) Come up with a wow factor that highlights Hainan is progressive and unique.

7.1. Purposeful and Consistent Action

Once adopted, there needs to be long-term commitment. With the new 5-year plan cycle starting in Hainan, aligning this campaign with it would be ideal. To launch the new branding campaign for Hainan, all messages and content about the destination must be consistent with the core message. Hainan needs to reduce the random noise and focus on the branding strategy. Initially, this might cause some disruptions and confusion, but ultimately, this type of focus will shorten the time required to establish a brand. More importantly, this approach will reduce the noise level that is causing a saturation of unfocused messages generated from Hainan. The key concept of this approach is as follows. Instead of throwing everything at random, hoping it will hit the target, we are taking a sniper approach to deliver a consistent message to the target audience we identified. To have a successful branding program, Hainan needs centralized planning that involves all parts of Hainan, both the private and public sectors, moving in unison with a shared purpose and motivation.

7.2. “Buy-In” from All Parts

Cannot assume that just because we say it, everyone in Hainan will understand. For example, the Hainan FTP is a major, fast-moving initiative. Do all parts of the public sector understand the scope and detail of the plan, and do they proactively know how to prepare to make it successful? Does the private sector, which is an essential part of the full implementation of the Hainan FTP, understand its role and have plans to fulfil it, thereby ensuring the Hainan FTP's success? This process of building complete “buy-in” will take time, but it is an essential step. For all media outlets, implementing the new branding strategy is crucial, but the public sector cannot decide on every little piece of content. However, it is precisely the accumulation of all content that will determine the success of the new branding campaign. An analysis of all Hainan content shows that most are at the tertiary level of branding or below. This is like throwing jigsaw puzzle pieces at the recipient of the message and asking them to put the pieces together to figure out the whole story of Hainan. Policy changes without full buy-in will have a lesser impact. Proper branding and its understanding across all parts of Hainan are needed to make the policy change more effective.

Another example is the airports in Hainan. It is where the majority of outside visitors will form their first and last impressions of Hainan. In the era of Hainan FTP, did we change how we greet visitors from outside? How can Hainan make “hello and goodbye” more impactful for the visitors? This is where a branding campaign for Hainan can have an impact. Imagine the airport experience as a branding opportunity for visitors. It is not just a place where you go through immigration, but one where a strong first impression can be made. What if the new brand is visible at every entry point, so visitors experience a positive entry with a brand slogan purposefully visible while they wait in the immigration line? What if the immigration officers smiled and spoke simple English? How will that impact Hainan’s image and reinforce Hainan’s brand? Another practical example is how Hainan can lower barriers to foreign visitors spending money there. For foreign visitors, can the Hainan banking system and other commercial venues accept foreign credit cards and other foreign electronic

payment systems? This is a good example of how the private sector can develop a solution to support our branding direction. We cannot say “Hainan is Yours,” then say it is only for people who speak Chinese and only for people with a domestic payment system. To say we are different and actually making sure that we are different will require much persuasion, training, and extra work.

7.3. *Saying vs Doing*

Actions will define Hainan’s branding initiative, not words. Words may get people to visit Hainan, but actions will have them come back or even live and work here. To ensure our words are consistent with our actions, we need to make examples to demonstrate that Hainan is heading in the right direction. Here are some examples of restrictions in China that Hainan can deregulate to illustrate the difference. We want visitors to Hainan to have a positive experience. We want them to share this experience with their network back home. However, many of their apps to share their message and content are restricted in China. Hainan's opening of full internet access for foreign visitors will clearly demonstrate, through action, that Hainan is opening up and leading deregulation in China.

Also, the core objective of most North Asian immigration policies is to restrict rather than to be open. All the North Asian countries have been gradually deregulating their immigration policies. However, their action is to remove layers of restrictions rather than to make a dramatic change to the core philosophy that says, “We are open and welcome you.” This is an opportunity for Hainan. If Hainan can position itself as the “glass half full” case rather than the “glass half empty” case regarding travel and working visas for foreigners, the action will go a long way to support Hainan’s brand. A no-visa policy indeed exists in Hainan for tourists, but the overall procedures for foreigners to work there remain cumbersome. Make this into a “glass half full” case. Even if Hainan cannot change the procedure now, stating that the work visa policy will become much more streamlined over the next 5 years will establish Hainan as more receptive to the needs of foreign talent and companies. By framing this “glass half-full,” Hainan can, through words, show that it intends to be different from prevailing, more restrictive trends toward foreign workers worldwide. Moreover, when each action is streamlined, credibility will be built. A move toward more “free” movement of people will take place in Hainan. This will lead to greater openness and deregulation in China.

The key strategic branding implication is that actions will have much more impact than words. Therefore, stating the action plan first and then carrying it out will enhance Hainan's credibility. This is why branding is essential; all actions and words will be tied to support and be consistent with the brand. This is the power of branding: not only does it earn credibility with the recipients of Hainan’s branding message, but it also forces discipline and strategic initiatives within Hainan.

7.4. *Effective Communication*

It will be naïve to assume that because we say it, everyone will understand it. The media campaign will need to be super organized to target specific audiences and message recipients. It cannot be random. Targeting specific segments with a message delivery style the group is accustomed to is a practical approach. Targeted countries, age group, purpose of the message (information delivery or marketing for Hainan), message deliverer, and communication style must be customized for the specific audience. This can disrupt the current media content-creation machine’s output, but it is a necessary step toward more effective communication. What we need is not more content but creating content that actually gets read and seen by many targeted audiences.

Just because the content is in English does not mean it will be well-received in all English-speaking countries. People are more likely to trust and accept media content when it is delivered by someone with a similar profile. In this light, much English-language content produced by local media outlets in

Hainan is aimed at foreigners already in Hainan and the surrounding area. It is not clear how practical this approach will be in establishing a strong brand for Hainan abroad. We need to change how we communicate. Once developed, the plan for effective communication abroad can be shared with all media outlets in Hainan.

Also, Hainan hosts over 100 events throughout the year. Conferences, expos, forums, and cultural events draw many visitors to Hainan. This creates an opportunity for Hainan to “direct-market” to the event visitors. Perhaps, there should be a Hainan Branding booth at all these events. It is an opportunity to introduce Hainan in person with a branding-consistent message and information. It will be a powerful and effective branding implementation for Hainan.

Event/Product Category	Quantity	Main Content Description
International Events Held in Hainan	41	Covering international film festivals, consumer goods expositions, international sports events, international cultural exchanges, etc.
Hainan-related Events	34	Covering local characteristic festivals, cultural activities, sports events, industrial activities, etc.
National/International Events Focused on Hainan	42	Covering Boao Forum for Asia, international film festivals, international expositions, etc.
Total Number of Events	117	Covering various types of events from 2000 to 2025
Hainan Characteristic Products Branding Dimensions	11	Covering coffee, Li Brocade, tropical fruits, seafood products, characteristic tourism IP, etc.

Figure 15: All Conferences, Events Held in Hainan, 2024

Source: Various news releases and event announcements

7.5. Do Hainanese know about Hainan FTP and its Brand?

The public sector is moving quickly toward full implementation of the Hainan FTP. However, most average citizens of Hainan are unaware of the main policy. They do not know the full long-term benefits to Hainan, nor what they ultimately need to do to help facilitate the policy's success. Hainan needs a campaign to educate its people about this new and momentous event.

One way to communicate is to set up multiple websites and QR code links to upload all the necessary information. This is being done currently. However, this puts the burden of understanding and information extraction on the average Hainanese. One effective way to communicate with Hainanese about FTP issues is to use a simpler format. For example, if we can distil the essence of the Hainan FTP, its benefits to Hainan, and what everyone in Hainan needs to do into a simple 10-slide cartoon, we can start to raise baseline awareness. We target all students at all educational institutions. We make it available across all media channels, social media, and public areas. Run one set as an introduction and prepare the following sets to include more information.

Throughout history, whenever a society achieved great things, there was a mobilization of the masses with a shared understanding and purpose. Hainan needs Hainanese to fully understand the Hainan FTP's implications and benefits for Hainan, and what they need to do to help Hainan. Without this, Hainan FTP is just another big project that does not concern them. Without this awareness of and benefit from the Hainan FTP, the engagement and contributions of Hainanese will not be mobilized. Moreover, without their full participation, efforts to make Hainan an international

destination and business hub will take longer. Everyone in Hainan should be aware of the benefits of the Hainan FTP and what they need to do to help ensure success.

7.6. The Ultimate “Wow” Factor

Imagine creating a service call center to help people outside Hainan learn more about the province. Probably will need to hire a large number of people. Hainan will need to employ many multilingual staff, as many inquiries are likely to come from foreigners interested in travel and business in Hainan. Then Hainan needs to train them on everything they need to know about the province. Only after this process, the “Hainan International Call Center” will be operational to answer questions on business regulations, investment procedure, visa process, and travel. Since they can only work 8 hours a day, they will need to create three teams to cover a 24-hour shift. What if there is a straightforward solution that can accomplish all this, and if done right, can become the ultimate “wow” factor that can help to brand Hainan? Hainan needs a generative AI ambassador to serve as the Hainan information agent.

Generative AI technology has advanced to the point where a single AI agent can operate 24/7 across multiple languages and engage in hundreds of unique interactions simultaneously. They can answer questions, serve as a resource library, and act as a contact agent for more complex inquiries. The AI agent can do this around the clock without getting tired. They can be set up with a language-detection mode, so no language specialists are needed. Eventually, many destinations will likely adopt this. However, if done now, Hainan will have the first-mover advantage and help establish our brand in a meaningful way. We have a unique character, Kiki, a Hainan gibbon, to be made into an AI agent. If this development can be contained within Hainan through universities, it can have a very positive impact, as it can “jump start” specific AI industry development in Hainan. If a quick turnaround is needed, there are established companies abroad that can develop this AI agent using the best technology to meet Hainan’s specifications and requirements.

Figure 16: Kiki, Hainan Gibbon Character

Source: Souvenir Team of HNU-ASU International College, Student Entrepreneurship & Innovation Center

8. Conclusion

Opportunities await Hainan. It is uniquely positioned in China to usher in a new development model. If manufacturing, infrastructure development, and the property sector were the engines of economic prosperity for China over the past 50 years, the innovation, opening up, and deregulation in Hainan can serve as a blueprint for the rest of China to create new economic prosperity over the next 50 years. Hainan faces both a significant responsibility and a remarkable opportunity. This research project on Hainan's branding identified a strategic path for the province. Hainan's branding is not just a marketing campaign. It will force strategic decisions and planning on all parts of Hainan. This makes the task of creating a brand and implementing a strategy that much more challenging. The primary and secondary branding slogans of "Hainan, Naturally Yours," "Your Gateway to & from China," and "Experience Nature" highlight the unique assets of Hainan. They capture the opportunities in Hainan and the challenges that Hainan needs to overcome.

9. Appendix: Branding Success Story: Destination Bryan, Texas, USA

9.1. A Small Texas City Finding Its Identity

Bryan, Texas, is a modest city of approximately 83,980 residents as of 2020, according to the United States Census. The city is located in the heart of the “Texas Triangle,” within a three-hour drive of Dallas, Houston, and Austin. Bryan has long existed in the shadow of its neighboring city of College Station, home to Texas A&M University. The city has struggled to establish a distinct identity as a destination in its own right.

In July 2020, the City of Bryan established “Destination Bryan,” a nonprofit destination marketing organization (DMO), with a clear mission of “Strengthen our community by inspiring people to spend time and money in Bryan, Texas” (Figure 17). Although the town inevitably has weaknesses as a small rural community, what makes Bryan’s story compelling is not that it became a major tourism powerhouse, but that it found a sustainable formula that works for both residents and visitors. Through their efforts, Destination Bryan achieved measurable success, winning DMO of the Year at the 2022 Texas Destination Excellence Awards, breaking hotel revenue records, reaching a decade-long peak in hotel occupancy rates, and maintaining its authentic small-town character.

Figure 17: Destination Bryan Logo and Team Members

Source: <https://www.destinationbryan.com/about/>

9.2. The Bryan Formula for Success

9.2.1. Authentic Brand Identity: “Bryan Legends.”

Destination Bryan did not focus on constructing tourism attractions or amenities to compete with larger destinations. Instead, it chose to compete on authenticity. The central brand concept is “A Legend Reborn,” which embodies the idea that “Born of converging cultures and built on deep Texas roots, Bryan is a community filled with authentic stories, people, and places – our legends. Our legends are ever evolving while staying true to our Texas spirit.” This positions the city around what it genuinely possesses: real people with real stories.

In practice, this is a project that identifies local business owners and their unique, multi-generational stories and designates them as “Bryan Legend”: The Kyle House & Polite Coffee Roasters (real friendly coffee, roasted and served in a legendary setting), Catalena Hatters (Texas’s premier custom hat makers from the Catalena family), The Remnant of Nawlins (down-home Cajun cooking in the heart of the Brazos Valley), Ronin Farm & Restaurant (farm-to-kitchen restaurant set in the beautiful renovated historic Ice House), Zeitman’s Grocery Store (multi-generational Zeitman family’s local deli), The Queen Theatre (restored iconic Downtown Bryan landmark), Messina Hof Winery (local

winery with a long history), Taqueria Poblana (acclaimed for tacos al pastor in Texas), Milton Parker Estate B&B (beautiful bed and breakfast in a more than 140-year-old vintage setting), The La Salle Hotel (historic hotel more than 100 years old), and Brazos Valley African American Museum.

Additionally, Destination Bryan created an appealing “Bryan Legends” video series (see Figure 23) that won a 2022 award from the Texas Association of Convention & Visitor Bureaus (TACVB). This approach costs less than creating new attractions while generating emotional connections that manufactured tourism products cannot achieve. The “Legend Reborn” concept not only allows Bryan to honor its heritage while embracing contemporary evolution, but also enables local community members to take pride in their history.

Figure 18: Bryan Legends videos

Source: <https://www.youtube.com/@destinationbryan6316/playlists>

9.2.2. Community Engagement: The Ambassador Program

One of the strategic and creative ideas for promoting Bryan is its Ambassador Program, which trains residents and business owners to welcome visitors and share the town's history and stories of local businesses, including Bryan Legends. Anyone who wants to become an ambassador can participate in the training program and obtain certification with an Ambassador badge (See Figure 19). The goal of Destination Bryan is to certify as many residents as possible as ambassadors. This program serves multiple functions:

For visitors: Obtain authentic, informed interactions with residents that enhance visiting satisfaction

For residents: Learn about local offerings they may not know exist

For businesses: Expand networking and cross-promotion opportunities

For the DMO: Receive ground-level feedback to incorporate into tourism strategy

Figure 19: Ambassador certificate and training program

Source: Author's picture

9.2.3. Event Strategy: Create and Enhance

Destination Bryan employs a dual event strategy. It not only creates signature events but also enhances existing community celebrations, which are highly meaningful to residents. Destination Bryan develops and owns new events that become synonymous with Bryan's identity. However, Destination Bryan does not view independently organized events as competition. Instead, it actively partners with them, considering them Bryan's best resources, and naturally takes over the administrative roles to amplify existing traditions.

One significant existing event is called "First Friday." On the first Friday of every month, downtown Bryan transforms with live music, art demonstrations, local vendors, and interactive activities (Figure 4). Now celebrating 20 years, it has become a regional tradition, with free shuttles from the neighboring Texas A&M campus, making attendance effortless. Destination Bryan's efforts to enhance this event by providing supplies and administrative support demonstrate its sincere commitment to the local community and have earned tremendous support from residents.

Figure 20: First Friday Event

Source: <https://www.destinationbryan.com/firstfriday/activities/>

Most importantly, Destination Bryan supports over 30 community events annually, demonstrating that event strategy is not about one flagship festival but about creating a continuous rhythm of reasons to visit and celebrate. Below is a selected list of created signature events and enhanced existing events:

Created signature events

- Lights on! – Annual holiday kick-off where the community gathers to countdown the illumination of thousands of lights along Main Street and Bryan Avenue.
- Hullabaloo Music Fest – Multi-venue, multi-genre music festival during Labor Day weekend.
- Downtown Bryan Street & Art Fair - Local artists fill Historic Downtown Bryan with hands-on art demonstrations, a wide variety of artworks for sale, live performances, and more.
- Enhanced existing events
- First Friday – Monthly downtown transformation featuring live music, art demonstrations, local vendors, and interactive activities.
- Brazos Valley Fair & Rodeo – Traditional Texas fair culture.
- Messina Hof Harvest Festival – Wine country celebration at Texas's renowned winery.

9.2.4. Digital Engagement: Trail Passport System

Destination Bryan understands that the current generation enjoys interactive and mobile-friendly experiences. Rather than simply listing attractions on a website or pamphlet, it created a digital passport program that transforms exploration into an engaging game.

The first and most successful program was the Bryan Taco Trail. 1. It featured more than 44 authentic taquerias, Mexican restaurants, and fusion taco offerings across the city, from traditional taquerias attached to gas stations to trendy downtown fusion spots. This effectively guides visitors beyond obvious tourist areas into authentic neighborhoods they would never discover otherwise.

The passport system concept is simple but effective:

- 1) Visitors sign up for a free digital passport via smartphone.
- 2) When visiting a participating restaurant, they "check in" through the app.
- 3) Check-ins accumulate points redeemable for exclusive prizes.
- 4) Completing all 44 stops earns a "Bryan Taco Trail Champion" flag and permanent recognition on the virtual Wall of Fame.

Following the successful outcomes from the Taco Trail, Destination Bryan created two additional digitally engaged programs: the "Aggieland Art Trail"² and "Bryan, Texas History Tour."³

¹ <https://www.destinationbryan.com/eat-drink/tacos/>

² <https://www.destinationbryan.com/things-to-do/arts-culture-history/art-trail/>

³ <https://www.destinationbryan.com/history/>

Figure 21: Digital engagement programs

Source: Destination Bryan website

9.2.5. Strategic Infrastructure: Sports Tourism Investment

Destination Bryan understood the importance of physical infrastructure in sustaining long-term growth for the town. The opening of Legends Event Center in December 2022 exemplifies how strategic infrastructure investment, in partnership with the City of Bryan, amplifies destination marketing efforts. Legends Event Center⁴ is an 11,100+ square-meter multipurpose sports and entertainment complex featuring: 1) 16 volleyball courts, 2) 8 basketball courts, 3) 4 NCAA-approved sand volleyball courts, 4) a 6,000 square-meter special event floor, 5) a 230 square-meter indoor Turf Area, 6) a 510 square-meter banquet room, 7) a gaming arena and Esports lounge, and more. This facility positions sports tourism as a long-term economic driver rather than a one-time investment for the town.

Figure 22: Legends Event Center

Source: <https://www.sportsdestinations.com/spotlights/texas/legends-event-center-texas-ultimate-sports-and-33603>

⁴ <https://bryanlegends.com/>

9.3. Bryan's Success Formula

Destination Bryan demonstrates that a small city with limited resources can achieve meaningful tourism and branding success without losing its authentic character. By focusing on genuine local stories, engaging residents as advocates, strategically managing events, leveraging digital tools, and partnering on infrastructure development, Bryan transformed from a city overshadowed by its neighbor into a recognized destination that benefits both visitors and the community.

Destination Bryan's experience suggests a replicable formula for destination seeking sustainable success: Authentic Identity + Community Ownership + Strategic Events + Digital Tools + Infrastructure Partnership = Sustainable Destination Success (See Table 1).

Table 1: Bryan's Success Formula

Component	Key Principles
Authentic Identity	Build a brand around genuine local stories; focus on unique strengths rather than competing on weaknesses.
Community Ownership	Ambassador programs turn residents into advocates, benefiting both locals and visitors.
Strategic Events	Create signature events while enhancing existing community celebrations.
Digital Tools	Guide visitor behavior toward local businesses through gamification and data collection.
Infrastructure Partnership	Align marketing with physical development to ensure long-term growth.

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海南品牌塑造

海南大学-亚利桑那州立大学联合国际学院（HAIC）学生创业与创新中心（SEIC）开展的白皮书研究

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海南品牌塑造

1. 引言

自 2025 年 12 月起，海南岛已全面启动自由贸易港建设 (China Daily, 2025) 当前正迈入新的发展阶段。未来几年，海南将面临更多机遇和挑战：更开放、更全球化、更复杂、更具创新性和更加繁荣。本文将聚焦海南发展需求的一个核心议题：海南应如何打造自身品牌？这一议题本身涵盖范围极广，对海南省有重要的战略意义。恰当的品牌塑造将以我们期望的方式向世界展示海南。打造海南品牌将使该岛在国际社会中的形象呈现获得战略性掌控。海南品牌将传递清晰独特的理念，激发人们对海南的兴趣。在全球市场竞争激烈的今天，众多旅游目的地争相博取关注，塑造海南品牌正是提升海南在国际消费者和企业中地位的必要举措。

品牌建设本质上是长期工程。众多企业和旅游目的地投入大量资源推广品牌。成功的品牌建设需要基于完善分析的连贯规划，执行过程需要配备专项预算以及系统性战略以持续强化品牌价值。成功的品牌项目需要时间、金钱与持续投入。

例如，众所周知，全球旅游业竞争异常激烈。由于真正“独具特色”的旅游目的地寥寥无几，许多地区正采用营销驱动、价格竞争的策略来吸引国际游客和企业。许多目的地并未聚焦可持续发展或独特的体验，而是将游客总数作为衡量成功的标准。(Jose Luis Ruiz-Real, 2020) 为了评估基于目的地物理属性的竞争力，我们分析比较了东南亚的国际热带旅游目的地。结论之一是：若仅以海南地理位置和“热带”魅力作为核心卖点，打造独特品牌将面临巨大挑战。

此外，我们不仅关注主要品牌建设，也关注二级和三级品牌建设。海南整体品牌战略的深度将超越单纯向岛外传递正确信息，更关注助力海南统筹发展布局。这是一项复杂的工程，但它能够将发展战略和路径制度化，实现资源优化配置，并兼顾社会责任，同时保留海南的独特气质。通过科学的品牌规划，可以避免牺牲长期资产以换取短期经济收益的传统模式。

经分析海南独特属性并结合中央及海南省的发展目标，我们确立“海南，自然属于你 (Hainan, Naturally Yours)”作为最能彰显海南精髓的主品牌标语。二级品牌将着重强调海南的两个显著特点：原始自然风光和商业机遇，分别为“体验自然 (Experience Nature)”和“您通往中国的门户 (Your Gateway to and from China)”。基于这些主次品牌理念，我们开展了全面的研究，制定了具体实施计划和专项项目建议。

海南发展路径的精神内核，正如其新近提出的“自由贸易区”倡议所体现，在于创造新的机遇而非争夺全球市场份额。基于此，我们建议海南的整体品牌建设应立足自身优势和资源，以此为核心为海南创造经济繁荣与稳定开辟创新之路。主品牌“海南，自然属于你 (Hainan, Naturally Yours)”及其子品牌“体验自然 (Experience Nature)”和“中国门户 (Your Gateway to and from China)”将共同实现这些核心目标。

2. 品牌塑造为何重要？

我们每天都会接触到大量的产品、服务、公司和目的地的广告。有些令人记忆深刻，有些则会被遗忘。即使价值相近，我们有时仍愿意为某些特定产品支付更高的价格。为何会产生记忆偏好与溢价行为？关键在于产品与服务建立的情感联结及其引发的感受 (Sheikh Farhan Ashraf, 2017)。事实上，在功能相近的情况下，某些品牌形象突出的智能手机企业的营业利润率高达 20%-30%。在竞争激烈的科技产品行业，这部分额外的利润足以显著提升企业的市场

估值（数据来源：美国证券交易委员会数据库）。正因如此，众多企业投入大量精力和资源用于品牌建立与推广。

为了吸引全球旅行者的目光，各个旅游目的地都在投入资源打造品牌形象。2024年，全球旅游市场总规模将达到11.5万亿美元(World Tourism Market, 2024)。按经济规模排名，国际旅游市场将位列全球第三，约为日本或德国的三倍（世界银行，2024）。为了在这个庞大的市场中占据一席之地，众多目的地正积极打造品牌形象。部分地区采用非常巧妙的策略凸显特色以吸引游客。例如，金字塔、极光、波利尼西亚和长城等词汇，无需直呼地名就能将人们与这些地点联系起来。这些都是强有力的地域品牌塑造典范——单词或图像就能与特定地点建立关联。然而，许多目的地面临着缺乏鲜明独特属性的品牌建设困境。

目的地品牌建设是备受研究的课题，众多地区都在寻求合适的策略来争夺全球市场份额。研究得出明确结论：虽然品牌塑造方式多样，但许多品牌缺乏独特的物理特征。部分地区采用情感触发机制进行品牌塑造。（Jose Luis Ruiz-Real, 2020）。

图1 旅游推广横幅

资料来源：各官方旅游局

在竞争激烈的目的地品牌建设中，海南面临的挑战在于如何真正捕捉海南的独特魅力，并将其清晰地传达给全球市场。首要任务是识别海南能够真正吸引国际游客的独特属性。其次需要精准整合这些特质，形成海南的吸引力体系。当前面临的挑战在于核心特质的矛盾性——既是热带岛屿，又是自由贸易港。海南的品牌塑造需要将椰林风光和繁忙港口的意象融合，向全球游客和企业传递统一信息。此外，承诺无法兑现的品牌终将失败。如果某地主打冰雪旅游却缺乏实际雪景资源，那么它既无法吸引回头客，更将招致负面舆论。这对海南而言影响尤为深远。要有效打造海南品牌，全岛多方力量需要合作，共同支持新品牌战略。这虽使实施过程更为复杂，但长远来看能助力海南更好地应对挑战与机遇。

3. 东南亚热带目的地品牌塑造趋势

3.1. 东南亚四个旅游目的地的比较研究

海南位于东南亚热带旅游胜地的核心区域（见图2）。该省身处高度竞争的区域旅游环境，周边有宿务（菲律宾）、巴厘岛（印度尼西亚）、普吉岛（泰国）和岘港（越南）等成熟的热带旅游目的地。这些目的地经过数十年的发展，凭借强大的目的地品牌建设、多元化的旅游产品组合以及相对成熟的治理和营销体系，已成长为全球知名的旅游枢纽。其发展轨迹展现了东南亚沿海以及岛屿目的地如何依托自然资源、文化魅力和国际连通性实现旅游业的持续增长。

图2：南海及周边国家地图。

资料来源：大英百科全书公司

将海南置于这一区域比较背景下，为评估其旅游发展与品牌战略提供了重要的分析基准。尽管海南拥有相似的环境特征和市场诉求，但运作环境存在显著差异：包括制度、政策和国内市场条件，以及政府主导的自由贸易港建设新举措。因此，比较视角有利于更细致地理解海南的市场定位和发展机遇。我们通过对比这些目的地的国际游客数据，为海南确立了参考基准。

图3 2024 年国际游客数量 (百万)

资料来源：海口出入境总站、Badan Pusat Statistik 巴厘岛省政府、宿务新闻、普吉岛移民局、岷港统计局

如图 3 所示，其他热门东南亚热带旅游目的地的外国游客数量远超海南。这些目的地发展成熟，拥有悠久的吸引外国游客的历史。仅凭“热带”概念，海南在与这些成熟的旅游胜地的竞争中将面临严峻挑战。

图 4：2024 年外国游客人均消费额

资料来源：越南统计局、印度尼西亚中央统计局、泰国银行、菲律宾政府

图 4 显示，2024 年东南亚热门旅游目的地的外籍游客人均消费水平基本持平。各目的地密切监测该数据，将其作为衡量外国游客消费行为的重要指标。（KPMG，2025）由于政策未发生重大调整，这些数据呈现稳定态势，仅存在轻微波动。当目的地放宽签证政策提升入境便利度时，消费数据才会出现显著变化。该地区吸引外国游客的竞争日益激烈。海南岛的外国游客消费数据获取难度较大。根据 KPMG 的一项研究，外国游客在海南的平均消费额约为中国游客的两倍。此外，随着海南全岛自由贸易港地位的全面落实，两项重大的政策调整也将影响游客消费模式和出行规律。

以下是各旅游目的地面向全球市场塑造品牌吸引力的示例（见图 5）。

图 5：目的地品牌

资料来源：各官方旅游局

3.2 “热带风情”已趋于饱和

在此背景下，将海南定位为泛化的“热带”旅游目的地存在战略局限性，因为东南亚的热带旅游形象已被众多历史悠久且全球知名的品牌占据。巴厘岛、普吉岛和宿务等目的地围绕共同的气候和海岸特征，已构建起强大的情感叙事和视觉标识，仅凭“热带”属性进行差异化竞争的效果正在日益减弱（见图 6）。对于海南而言，这种饱和状态凸显了其超越传统热带品牌定位的必要性，需要依托其独特的政策框架、文化景观和发展轨迹，构建更具辨识度的价值主张。若想给海外游客和企业留下深刻的第一印象，仅围绕“热带”构建的品牌形象无法传递恰当且独特的信息；因此海南的品牌定位必须另辟蹊径。

图6: 巴厘岛、普吉岛、宿务、岷港的宣传图片

资料来源: 各官方旅游局

3.3 中国国内热门旅游目的地

与国内其他热门旅游目的地相比,我们发现许多目的地都围绕着实体旅游景点进行品牌塑造。这些标志性景点已成为海外人士心中中国的代名词。为了吸引海外游客的关注,海南面临着巨大的挑战。海南如何在中国长城和兵马俑面前定位?答案是不应强行定位。此外,随着海南自由贸易港的全面启动,其定位已不仅限于度假胜地,这使得海南打造独特品牌更加困难。

图7: 年度游客访问量

资料来源: 各地方政府机构

官方宣传标语	
长城	不到长城非好汉
紫禁城	和我们一起探索世界
西安	唐诗之都
上海	这里是上海

图 8：中国各景点及热门旅游城市的官方旅游标语

资料来源：各地方政府机构

3.4 海南的独特品质

3.4.1. 未受破坏的自然

海南是一座热带岛屿。然而与其他成熟的热带旅游目的地相比，海南的游客数量和基础设施建设（受游客容量限制）相对滞后。有人认为，海南需要建设更多度假村和基础设施以增强竞争力。我们对此持不同意见。其实，海南最宝贵的资产恰恰是偏远村庄未开发的自然风貌和生活方式。这正是海南独一无二的财富——未经雕琢的自然。

海南的一些有利条件包括：拥有原始海滩的小渔村；保留着传统农耕的热带果园；生态完整的热带雨林；以及至今仍保留着传统生活方式的各类村落（火山村、黎族村和苗族村）。这片未被破坏的自然与质朴生活方式依然存在于海南，理应成为海南品牌建设的支柱。

此外，海南拥有中国首个热带雨林国家公园——海南热带雨林国家公园，这里保护着国内最高水平的生物多样性及特有物种。国家公园体系为海南提供了难得机遇，使其能够将目的地品牌建设以保护为导向的发展、生态管理、健康旅游及其他低影响旅游模式结合。与大众化的度假胜地不同，海南可以定位为以自然保护、文化传承和社区生计为核心的“活态景观。这些特质为差异化的品牌战略奠定了坚实基础——强调真实体验、生态完整性和长期可持续性，而非规模扩张和客流数量。

与此同时，海南正崛起为体育旅游的重要枢纽，陆续承办冲浪、自行车、帆船、跑步和耐力运动等国际国内赛事。该岛得天独厚的自然条件——绵延的海岸线、巍峨山脉、茂密森林以及全年温暖的气候——使得体育和户外休闲活动得以融入原始风貌的自然景观，而非局限于人工建造的巨型场馆。这种模式为体育旅游与自然保护、养生和 slow tourism 理念相结合创造了契机，强化了海南作为活力与自然共生的旅游目的地的形象。当体育旅游与国家公园体系及乡村社区相融合时，更将超越传统的热带度假模式的局限。深化海南独特的旅游身份认同。

3.4.2. 海南自由贸易港 (FTP)

海南的另一独特之处在于，中国已将整个海南省指定为自由贸易港。随着中国出口导向型和制造业导向型增长时代步入成熟阶段，海南自由贸易港肩负着“以高标准建设海南自由贸易港，推动海南高质量发展，助力全国新发展格局”的使命。(China Daily, 2025). 这是一项艰巨的任务——海南自由贸易港要为中国探索新的发展路径。虽然充满挑战，但也正是海南品牌建设中至关重要的独特优势。

挑战在于如何将这两个看似无关的概念融入同一个品牌规划中。某种程度上，这两个独特的属性不仅差异显著，而且含义“截然相反”——树木葱郁、海滩洁净的自然景象与繁忙港口和工厂林立的港口码头形象形成了强烈碰撞。海南的品牌塑造必须提炼这两大要素的精髓，凝练成统一概念。

图9：三亚和海口港附近海滩的库存照片

来源：beach-on-map.com, alamy.com

3.5. 品牌塑造引发情感共鸣

许多品牌推广方案都聚焦于地理位置及描述性词汇，这容易引发受众基于图像的联想。而我们则专注于海南品牌的情感触发机制。我们选择的品牌标语并非简单的描述，而是旨在唤起情感，传递感受而非仅仅描绘图像(Rovika Prem, 2025)。这正是融合海南两大截然不同的核心资产——自然风光和FTP（自由贸易港）——的最佳途径。

采取这种策略有两个原因。首先，海南的品牌形象必须与众不同。海南需要非传统的品牌战略来推广其独特优势。在如今视频信息爆炸的时代，人们对视频信息的记忆停留时间非常短暂，基于图像的信息难以留下持久的印象。此外，这种聚焦情感触发的策略，与海南希望传达给受众的信息相契合，凸显了海南的独特性。成功的海南品牌项目应该传递积极、差异化的信息，并最终促成潜在的行动。

4. 向海南推出“海南，自然属于你”品牌

图10：海南，自然属于你

来源：作者图表

4.1 核心品牌标语

通过结合“海南 (Hainan)”和“自然属于你 (Naturally Yours)”，这句品牌标语能够引发多层次的情感共鸣。第一层含义非常直接：海南即自然，海南属于你，两者都充满吸引力。这种表达避免直接宣扬自身优势，转而暗示整座岛屿皆可供游客亲身体验。“自然”一词凸显原始生态、淳朴村落和清新空气。“属于你”则强调了海南自由贸易港的优势，并传递出一种个性化的体验。

4.2 外籍教师非正式调查

为了评估该标语的有效性，我们对本校的国际教师展开了非正式问卷调查。在 40 份问卷邀请中，共收集到 33 份回复。图 11 展示了调查结果。

图 11：外籍教师调查结果

资料来源：本研究报告作者

根据调查结果，“海南，自然属于你”这一标语引发了复杂但总体积极的反应，其中好奇（30.3%）和感兴趣（24.2%）是最常见的初始反应。“自然属于你”这一表述最强烈关联到海南的自然环境（36.4%）和归属感（33.3%），表明该标语有效地传达了生态保护与情感共鸣的双重诉求。受访者清晰地捕捉到该标语所传达的双重寓意，绝大多数受访者都意识到了“海南属于你”（75.8%的受访者表示强烈/比较认同）和“海南即自然”（81.8%的受访者表示）的内涵。总体而言，该标语获得了积极评价，57.6%的受访者认为其“好”或“非常好”。但值得注意的是，仍有部分受访者（21.2%）持中立或负面态度，表明该标语在信息清晰度和情感共鸣度方面仍有改进空间。

定性反馈为我们深入了解该标语的接受度提供了细致入微的洞察。尽管部分受访者认为该口号听起来像泛泛的营销标语或者不够直观，但这些反馈恰恰凸显了通过独特的视觉识别和切实行动来支持该标语的重要性，以避免沦为陈词滥调的印象。相反，其他参与者则明确指出该标语传递出一种包容性和归属感，直接肯定了“Yours”所预期的情感共鸣。此外，该标语既被解读为探索海南自然环境的邀请，又被理解为对环境本身的指涉，证实了其双重层面的信息传递取得成功。总而言之，这些多元反馈表明标语虽然成功植入引人入胜的概念种子，但其最终影响力仍需依托所有接触点的持续且真诚的落地执行。

从品牌建设角度来看，调查结果表明，“海南，自然属于你（Hainan Naturally Yours）”虽奠定了坚实的战略基础，但无法作为独立的强力传播语。其优势在于成功地将自然元素与情感叙事相结合，这与海南作为独特疗愈目的长期定位高度契合。然而，中立和批评意见表明，该标语需要通过连贯的故事叙述、地域特色视觉呈现以及与政策产品协同的呈现方式来精心激活，避免沦为泛泛品牌印象。战略层面而言，海南品牌建设应减少对标语创新的投入，更着力于将“自然属于你（Naturally Yours）”的承诺转化为具体的沉浸式体验、治理实践以及切实的变革，从而提升品牌的可信度，塑造差异化形象。

5. 二级品牌标语

如前所述，海南的独特魅力体现在两个方面：一是原始的自然风貌，二是自由贸易港建设——这代表了中国经济发展的新路径。在二级品牌推广工作中，需要通过两条标语分别彰显海南魅力的双重资产。

5.1. 原始自然与质朴生活

“体验自然(Experience Nature)”通过“自然而然(Naturally)”的措辞呼应核心标语。这种对自然的强调既涵盖海南的品牌定位也体现其能为游客提供的独特体验。例如，体验偏远渔村的淳朴生活、火山村落的奇幻风情、少数民族村落的传统韵味，以及原始热带雨林的静谧氛围。这些正是海南为追求清幽放松度假体验的游客提供的独特选择。尽管自然旅游本身并非新概念，但在后疫情时代，随着旅行者日益追求能修复身心、支持情感健康的低密度环境，其重要性和需求显著增强（Buckley & Westaway, 2020; Ma 等, 2021）。以宁静、简约和与自然连接为核心的体验，顺应了人们对健康、慢旅行以及深度地域互动的时代潮流。在此背景下，海南相对完好的自然和文化景观使其具备满足新兴市场需求的独特优势。围绕“恢复力、韧性与健康”构建“体验自然”的框架，既强化了战略意义，又与长期可持续发展目标相契合。与此同时，中国年轻一代对自然和户外旅游的兴趣日益浓厚，包括徒步旅行、远足、露营、豪华露营、冲浪和房车旅游（Hu et al., 2025; Lu et al., 2022; Wengel et al., 2022; Wengel et al., 2024），这反映了生活方式价值观的转变以及人们对自由、沉浸式体验和自

然体验的渴望。我们将在后文中对此概念进行更详细的阐述。

5.1.1. 缓解城市压力

城市生活的密集化催生了一种复杂的压力，其成因包括环境拥挤、社会压力、经济竞争、数字信息饱和以及日益加快的生活节奏。对许多城市居民而言，休闲旅行已难以实现真正的身心恢复，因为假期往往复制了城市中常见的快节奏、刺激和以绩效为导向的行为模式。这种常被称为“需要从假期中休假”的现象，凸显了旅行与恢复功能日益割裂的现状。在此背景下，海南岛有潜力将定位为慢节奏、简约生活和心灵重连的理想之地。海南岛的价值并非局限于热带地区的狭隘视角，而在于其多样化的自然环境中，包括热带雨林、沿海生态系统、农耕景观、火山地貌和国家公园保护区。这些空间让游客能够暂时摆脱都市的喧嚣，重新接轨自然循环，获得感官享受，回归到注重当下而非效率为优先的日常生活模式。

慢旅行是这一定位的核心。在乡村地区长期驻留、参与采摘水果等小型农事活动、进行徒步等低强度户外休闲活动、体验当地文化习俗，都鼓励游客进行更深入、更少掠夺性的旅游。这样的体验让游客能够摆脱持续的数字连接，减轻认知负担，实现对城市压力的“排毒”。从这个意义上讲，简约本身就成为旅游资源，它提供都市环境中日益稀缺的闲暇时光、宁静氛围和自由体验。

户外运动类活动进一步强化了这种疗愈功效。徒步旅行、远足、骑行、冲浪、划船、露营/豪华露营等自然活动既能促进身心健康，还能提升思维清晰度、情绪调节能力，并建立与地域的深层联结。当这些活动植根于自然乡村景观而非商业化的度假环境时，既能推动整体福祉而不强化高消费或者高压旅游模式，又能为当地经济提供可持续支持。

文化与乡村旅游在这一疗愈框架中也发挥着关键作用。探访传统村落、渔村和少数民族文化，能让人们以全新视角审视时间流逝、社会关系以及人与自然互动。这些体验有助于反思、文化学习和获得情感慰藉，同时也为偏远社区创造可持续发展的经济机遇。总而言之，以自然为基础、慢节奏且植根文化的旅游模式，使海南不仅成为逃离喧嚣的避风港，更成为应对当代都市压力的疗愈之地，是获得身心净化、重获平衡和实现长期福祉的理想之所。

5.2 海南：通往中国与通往世界的门户

“您通往中国的门户（Your Gateway to & from China）”是另一条辅助品牌宣传标语，它抓住了海南为省外企业和投资者提供的机遇。正如中国领导人所指出的，海南自由贸易港（FTP）的实施具有全国性意义。因此，只有当海南成为通往中国的门户时，其真正的吸引力才能得到充分体现。在许多发展中国家，外国商品和投资的流动方向通常被认为是单向的——资金和人员的流入。海南对外贸易的真正优势在于商品流动和资金流动的双向，而海南正是这一活动的枢纽。通过将“进出双向”的概念融入标语，我们强调了海南应有的双向角色定位。随着海南自由贸易港（FTP）的建立，这里已成为外国企业和投资者进入中国市场的理想据点。此外，国内外企业亦可以利用海南作为对外门户，将中国推向世界。我们希望人们对这条标语的第一反应是“为什么？如何实现？”。这种认知触发效果极佳，能体现了受众的思考和参与。为此，必须建立一套简便全面的信息传递体系来支持这一品牌标语。

图 12：海南品牌标语的三层结构

资料来源：本研究报告作者

5.2.1. 亲近自然，享受现代便利

依托自由贸易港建设，海南成为将高品质的自然环境与现代都市系统的可靠舒适性融合的旅游目的地。自由贸易港框架加速了对交通基础设施、数字互联、医疗保健、物流和国际标准服务的投资，消除了传统自然与乡村旅游的诸多障碍。游客得以高效地往来于机场、城市、村落、海岸线和自然保护区之间，灵活地选择旅行方式，既能沉浸于自然美景，又能享受现代化的便利和安全。这种混合定位在后疫情时代的旅行偏好中尤为重要——便捷性、健康安全和可预测性已成为决策的关键因素。海南让旅行者能够享受慢旅行、户外休闲和文化体验，同时规避偏远目的地常见的风险与后勤难题。短途交通、涵盖不同价位的高品质住宿选择以及可靠的数字服务，为长期停留、远程办公和深度自然体验提供了支持。这使海南对渴望疗愈之旅却需要兼顾工作与家庭责任的都市居民极具吸引力。

从战略角度来看，现代便利设施与自然环境可达性的共生关系，使海南得以发展独具特色的“自然+”旅游模式。游客白天可以体验森林、乡村、海岸风光和国家公园，必要时也能便捷地获取医疗、交通和城市配套服务。这种模式降低了选择自然旅游的心理和实际成本，并将潜在市场从冒险型或高流动性群体拓展至更广泛人群。

重要的是，该模式同样支持可持续发展目标。将现代基础设施集中于现有城市节点，同时对周边自然与乡村区域实施受控准入，有助于防止敏感景观过度开发。当与分区规划、游客管理和社区旅游框架相协调时，自由贸易港就能成为平衡发展的推动力。从这个意义上讲，海南并非自然与现代化的权衡取舍之地，而是两者相得益彰的旅游目的地，为当代经济环境下以自然为主导、以福祉为目标的旅游业提供了一条切实可行的发展路径。

海南的另一大独特之处在于自然景观的便捷可达性。海南所有自然保护区和传统淳朴生活目的地均可从高铁站或主要公路轻松抵达。海口更是一座完美诠释“tropical urbanism”的城市。它拥有媲美国际大都市的现代化基础设施，同时又能便捷通达自然。在这里，人们既可以在具有全球竞争力的企业环境中工作，又能享受热带地区原始自然的馈赠。对于任何希望借“中国门户”之势谋求发展的个人或公司而言，这都是极具吸引力的选择。

6. 自然旅游的定义和概念

海南传统上以“3S 旅游”（阳光、大海、沙滩）为重点，这在推动经济发展和提升旅游市场的知名度方面成效显著（Ferreira et al., 2024）。然而，这种侧重如今可能会限制海南岛实现更广泛国际认可的潜力，这与公共及私营部门利益相关方的共同愿景存在落差。要突破“东方夏威夷”的定位，关键在于实现旅游产品多元化，以应对区域竞争、游客需求变化以及环境挑战。

幸运的是，海南拥有丰富的自然、人文和文化资源，如果能够巧妙整合，便可打造出竞争对手难以复制的独特竞争优势。在这种产品多元化战略中，“自然”元素依然是旅游产品的核心。同时，我们要提升海南山区内陆地区在旅游发展中的地位，使其与沿海地区并驾齐驱。

6.1 海南应发展自然+旅游

我们建议海南打造一个融合海洋与雨林、涵盖养生、热带农业景观、南洋文化遗产、民族传统、生态环保、茶咖啡文化以及现代休闲活动的多层次旅游景观。这些元素应相互促进，共同构筑独具特色的“自然+旅游”产品。如此一来，多元化发展将强化海南的品牌形象而非削弱其辨识度。这一战略将有助于海南从单纯的海滩度假胜地转型为一个多维度探索的旅游目的地，同时保持其鲜明特色。

这种市场需求源于游客对超越传统旅游体验的本土化深度体验日益增长的渴望，学术界早已认识到这一点。然而，直到近期，旅游经济才开始重视并投入资源，而这往往是在知名咨询公司背书之后。因此，诸如 Destinations International (2019) 和 JLL (2018) 等主要咨询公司的行业报告均强调，消费者日益追求独特而真实的旅行体验。这一趋势已成为全球旅游目的地的首要任务，如果海南仍仅专注于全包式 3S 模式，则可能落后。

6.2 自然+旅游：海南乡村振兴

海南岛的“自然+旅游”（见图 13）是一种混合型旅游产品，它既能促进游客的生态健康，又能积极支持欠发达农村地区的振兴。它超越了传统的自然旅游模式，融入人文空间，例如迷人的民族村落、火山村落和农田景观，并融合南洋文化以及黎族和苗族等少数民族的非物质文化遗产元素。该模式实践慢旅行的理念，通过强调当地居民作为目的地核心角色，引导游客超越单纯风景消费。这与快节奏、往往流于表面的传统大众旅游体验截然不同，它鼓励游客放慢脚步，细细品味旅程，并深入体验所到之处。这意味着摒弃了现代旅游中常见的消费导向思维，转而将当地文化、人民和生态系统视为目的地的核心。慢旅行（Dickinson, 2015）培养了专注力和临在感，使游客能够真正欣赏海南岛的美丽和丰饶。

图13: Nature+ Tourism products (yellow), and development and management models (green)

Source: authors of this research report

基于此，生态健康（Reese & Myers, 2012）作为整体性框架，通过沉浸式和可持续的自然体验整合身体、心理和精神层面的福祉。其实现路径在于引导游客参与既能焕活身体又能滋养心灵的活动。例如，徒步穿越三亚附近郁郁葱葱的吊罗山雨林，探索海口附近荣滩村的古老火山地貌（Cimino et al., 2025），以及参与庆祝海南多元民族文化的当地节庆活动。其目标是促进游客与海南岛自然文化景观之间的深层联结，从而提升游客对海南独特资源的保护意识与珍视态度。

6.3. 再生旅游：提升旅游目的地的健康度

再生旅游的概念在塑造自然+旅游模式中发挥着关键作用。再生旅游（Bellato 等人，2023）旨在恢复和提升旅游目的地的健康水平，关注环境和当地居民的福祉。在海南岛实践中，需要推行既能最小化生态足迹又能促进乡村振兴的举措。这包括支持本土企业、投资可持续基础设施以及促进生物多样性保护。通过实践再生原则，自然+旅游旨在对环境和当地社区产生积极影响，确保旅游业的收益得到公平分配。同样在再生领域，永续旅游（Ferreira 等人，2021）借鉴了永续农业的原则，指导生态友好型住宿（例如，原则 6：利用和重视当地资源）、可持续食品系统（例如，原则 7：从模式到细节进行设计）以及社区项目（例如，融合而非隔离）的设计。这些原则强调顺应现有进程而非与之对抗，以创造兼具韧性和和谐性的环境。值得注意的是，再生旅游实践不仅能最小化环境影响，更能积极促进自然和人文景观的双重复兴。

6.4. 乡村社区对海南独特的品牌形象塑造至关重要

至关重要的是，农村社区在我们构建海南“自然+旅游”愿景中扮演着至关重要的角色。游客对真实体验的渴望无法被传统旅游的刻意包装所满足（Morais et al., 2017），这为本土微型企业填补这一空白提供了契机（KC et al., 2021）。尽管商机广泛，但最易于发展的是住宿业，包括民宿、青年旅舍和小型精品酒店，以满足不同游客的喜好和预算。毋庸置疑，在我们构想中，这些住宿场所将由村民拥有和运营，经济效益将直接惠及当地社区，杜绝资金外

流至企业集团。

总之，“自然+旅游”代表了一种前瞻性的可持续旅游模式，旨在实现游客生态健康的同时振兴乡村地区。通过践行再生旅游与永续旅游原则，自然+旅游超越传统自然旅游范畴，融入人性化空间设计，倡导 slow trip 理念，将当地社区置于核心地位。这种整体性可持续旅游模式有望为海南岛树立负责任、有内涵的旅游体验新标杆。

文本框 1：热带城市化

Tropical Urbanism 是一个研究较为深入的课题。全球城市化趋势如今已蔓延至热带地区，引发了人们对可持续发展的担忧。包括联合国在内的许多机构都对此进行了广泛的研究 (UN, 2015)。本节将重点关注与海南相关的两个具体问题：热带环境与城市环境之间的平衡，以及如何将这种平衡融入海南的整体品牌建设中。

海口是海南人口最多的城市（300 万），其次是三亚（100 万）。此外，还有几个城市人口不足 50 万。按照中国的标准，海南的城市中心规模较小。扩大城市规模是促进经济增长的途径之一。然而，这种做法可能会对海南的核心资产——岛屿原始自然环境——造成极大的破坏。

随着海南日益国际化与现代化，其面临的挑战在于平衡热带自然生态与都市生活。选择何种核心发展目标，将决定海南在保持天然禀赋的同时实现城市化的“成功”程度。海南最宝贵的财富之一便是其洁净的环境，必须加以保护和维护。若忽视这一点，海南的未来将与其他被城市化吞噬的热带地区如出一辙。全球有许多特大城市忽视了这种平衡的例子。即便在邻近的东南亚地区，这种平衡的转变也正在发生 (AQI, 2024)。

图 14：2024 年平均空气质量指数

资料来源：2024 年全球空气质量指数 (AQI) 报告

有一种观点认为，更高的建筑、更多的人口和更严重的交通拥堵将定义城市化的成功，并促进国际化；此外，空气和噪音污染也是城市化及其带来的经济繁荣所必须付出的代价。这似乎是任何雄心勃勃的城市中心走向国际化的公式和路径。如果海南将保护和可持续发展作为其首要发展目标，并专注于提高生活质量（而非数量）以实现国际化，又会如何呢？医疗保健、休闲娱乐、法律和金融服务以及教育都是城市居民（无论本地居民还是外籍人士）日常生活中必不可少的服务。通过让外国人更便捷地获得这些日常所需，就能实现吸引国际人才和热带城市化的目标。海南应将生态保护、可持续发展和提高生活质量作为其城市化框架的主要标准。这与

中央近期将海南定位为“国家生态保护试点区”的指导方针相契合 (China Daily, 2025)。海南可以提供一种全新的热带都市生活——既能在一个具有全球竞争力的环境中工作，享受便捷的服务，午休时间能去蔚蓝的大海上冲浪：这便是海南式的热带都市生活。

7. 品牌推广活动的实施

在实施一项重大新举措（例如海南品牌推广活动）时，需要遵循五条简单、合乎逻辑的规则。

- 1) 每个行动都需要目标明确且保持一致性。
- 2) 需要对所有相关方进行全面教育并获得其认同。这涵盖私营部门和公共部门。任何环节的滞后都会限制效率和最终成功。
- 3) 聚焦信息传递的清晰度，以受众理解为有效沟通的核心准则。
- 4) 提高公众意识。
- 5) 打造令人惊叹的亮点，突出海南的进步和独特性。

7.1. 有目的且持续的行动

一旦确定方向就需要长期坚持。随着海南新五年规划周期的启动，将此次品牌推广活动与之同步进行将是理想之选。为了启动海南新品牌推广活动，所有关于海南的信息和内容都必须与核心理念保持一致。海南需要减少杂乱无章的信息，专注于品牌战略。初期，这可能会造成一些混乱和干扰，但长期来看这种聚焦能缩短品牌建设周期。更重要的是，这种方法将减少信息噪音，避免产生大量分散的传播内容。该方法核心理念如下：摒弃漫无目的的广撒网式传播，转而采用狙击式精准投放——向明确界定的目标受众传递统一的信息。为了成功开展品牌推广活动，海南需要统筹全岛规划，让私营部门和公共部门朝着共同的目标和动力齐头并进。

7.2. 各主体的“参与”

不能因为我们说了，就认为海南的每个人都理解。例如，海南自由贸易港（FTP）是一项重大且快速推进的举措。公共部门的各环节是否真正了解该规划的范围和细节？是否主动掌握了确保其成功的准备工作？作为海南省自由贸易港全面实施的关键力量，私营部门是否明确自身职责并制定了相应的计划，从而确保海南省自由贸易港的成功实施？建立全民“认同”的过程需要时间，但这是必经的关键步骤。对于所有媒体而言，实施新的品牌战略至关重要，但公共部门无法决定每一个细节内容。然而，正是所有内容的积累将决定新品牌推广活动的成败。对所有海南相关内容的分析表明，大多数内容的品牌化程度处于三级或更低。这就像把拼图碎片扔给信息接收者，让他们自己拼凑出海南的全貌。缺乏全民理解认同，政策变革的影响将大打折扣。要使政策变革更加有效，需要进行恰当的品牌宣传，并确保海南全境都能理解其含义。

另一个例子是海南的机场。大多数外来游客都会在这里形成对海南的第一印象和最后印象。在海南自由贸易港（FTP）时代，我们是否改变了迎接外来游客的方式？海南如何才能让“你好”和“再见”给游客留下更深刻的印象？这正是海南品牌建设可以发挥作用的地方。不妨将机场体验想象成一个品牌推广的机会。机场不仅是通关场所，更能给人留下深刻第一印象。如果新品牌标识遍布每个入境点，让游客在排队等候入境时就能看到醒目的品牌标语，从而获得积极的入境体验，那会怎样？如果入境官员面带微笑，用简单的英语交流，又会怎样？这将如何影响海南的形象，并强化海南的品牌认知？另一个实际案例是海南如何降低外国游客在海南消费的门槛。对于外国游客来说，海南的银行系统和其他商业场所是否接受外国信用卡和其他外国电子支付方式？这正是私营部门如何开发解决方案支持我们品牌定位的绝佳范例。我们不能一

方面说“海南属于你”，另一方面又说它只面向讲中文的人，只面向使用国内支付系统的人。要真正实现差异化并确保落地需要大量的说服工作、培训投入和额外付出。

7.3. 言行一致

行动而非言辞将定义海南的品牌建设。空谈或许能吸引人们来海南旅游，但行动才能让他们再次光临，甚至在此生活工作。为了确保言行一致，我们需要以实际行动证明海南正朝着正确的方向前进。以下是海南可放宽的若干国内限制措施，以此彰显差异化优势。我们希望来海南的游客拥有积极的体验，并分享给家乡的社交圈。然而，许多用于分享信息和内容的应用程序在中国受到限制。海南向外国游客全面开放互联网接入，将以实际行动清晰地展现海南正在走向开放，并引领中国的开放浪潮。

此外，大多数北亚国家的移民政策核心目标是限制而非开放。尽管所有北亚国家都在逐步放松移民政策，但它们的行动只是移除层层限制，而非从根本上改变“我们开放，欢迎你们”的核心理念。这对海南来说是一个机遇。如果海南能够将自身定位为外国人旅游和工作签证方面“乐观”而非“悲观”的典范，这将极大地提升海南的品牌形象。海南目前确实对游客实行免签政策，但外国人在海南工作的整体流程仍然繁琐。不妨将这种情况转化为“乐观”的一面。即使海南现在无法改变现有流程，但承诺未来五年内将大幅简化工作签证政策，也能使海南展现出对外国人才和企业需求的积极响应。通过这种“乐观”的表述，海南可以用言辞表明其与全球范围内普遍存在的、对外国劳工更为严格的趋势有所不同。此外，当每一项举措都得到有效执行时，信誉也将随之建立。海南将朝着更加“自由”的人员流动方向发展。这将促进中国更加开放和放松管制。

战略品牌塑造的关键在于行动远胜于言辞。因此，先制定行动计划，再付诸实施，才能真正提升海南的信誉度。这就是品牌塑造至关重要的原因；所有行动和言辞都将与品牌紧密相连，并与品牌保持一致。这就是品牌塑造的力量：它不仅能赢得海南品牌信息受众的信任，还能促使海南内部形成纪律，并推动战略举措的实施。

7.4. 有效沟通

认为我们说了就能让所有人理解，未免过于天真。媒体宣传活动必须精心策划，精准定位目标受众和信息接收者，绝不能随意而为。针对不同群体，采用他们熟悉的传播方式是一种切实可行的策略。目标国家、年龄段、信息目的（信息传递或市场营销）、信息传递者以及沟通方式，都必须根据具体受众进行定制。这可能会扰乱当前媒体内容生产机制的输出节奏，但却是迈向更有效沟通的必要一步。我们需要的不是更多的内容，而是能够真正被众多目标受众阅读和看到的内容。

仅仅因为内容是英文的，并不意味着它就能在所有英语国家获得良好反响。人们更容易信任和接受由与他们背景相似的人发布的媒体内容。鉴于此，海南本地媒体制作的许多英文内容都面向已经在海南及周边地区的外国人。这种做法在为海南打造强大的海外品牌方面究竟有多大成效，目前尚不明朗。我们需要改变沟通方式。一旦制定出有效的海外沟通方案，即可与海南所有媒体共享。

此外，海南全年举办超过100场活动。会议、展览、论坛和文化活动吸引了众多游客来到海南。这为海南提供了一个直接面向活动游客进行市场推广的机会。或许，海南应该在所有这些活动中设立品牌推广展位。这是一个以统一的品牌信息和宣传方式进行面对面推介的良机，也将成为海南实施品牌建设的重要举措。

活动/产品类别	数量	主要内容描述
在海南举办的国际活动	41	涵盖国际电影节、消费品博览会、国际体育赛事、国际文化交流等。
海南相关活动	34	涵盖地方特色节庆、文化活动、体育赛事、工业活动等。
以海南为重点的国内/国际活动	42	涵盖博鳌亚洲论坛、国际电影节、国际博览会等。
活动总数	117	涵盖从2000年到2025年的各类活动。
海南特色产品品牌化维度	11	涵盖咖啡、黎锦、热带水果、海产品、特色旅游IP等。

图 15: 2024 年在海南举办的所有会议和活动

来源: 各类新闻稿和活动公告

7.5. 海南人了解海南自由贸易港及其品牌吗？

海南公共部门正迅速推进海南自由贸易港政策的全面实施。然而，大多数海南普通民众对这项核心政策并不了解。他们既不清楚这项政策将给海南带来的长期利好，也不知道自身应该如何助力政策落地。海南亟需开展全民宣传活动，让民众了解这项意义重大的新举措。

目前正在进行的一种沟通方式是建立多个网站和二维码链接并上传所有必要信息。然而，这给普通海南民众带来了理解和提取信息的负担。更有效的沟通方式是采用简化形式。例如，若能将海南外籍人才政策的核心要义、对海南的益处以及全岛居民的行动指南浓缩成 10 页卡通图示，即可建立基础认知。目标受众涵盖所有教育机构的学生群体，通过全媒体渠道、社交平台及公共场所进行传播。首轮投放基础版，后续版本逐步增加深度内容。

纵观历史，每当一个社会取得伟大成就时，总伴随着民众的动员，他们怀着共同的认知与目标。海南需要海南人充分理解海南自由贸易港对海南的意义与益处，以及他们需要为海南做些什么。

若缺乏这种共识，海南自由贸易港不过是又一个与他们无关的大项目。若没有这种

对海南自由贸易港的认知与受益意识，就无法激发海南人的参与热情与贡献力量。更重要的是，若缺少全民参与，海南建设国际旅游胜地和国际贸易枢纽的进程将被延缓。每位海南人都应认识到海南自由贸易港的利好，并明确自身助力成功责任。

7.6. 终极“Wow”因素

设想建立一个服务呼叫中心，帮助海南省外的民众深入了解该省。这可能需招聘大量人员。由于许多咨询可能来自对海南旅游和商业感兴趣的外国人，海南需雇佣大量多语种员工。随后海南需对员工进行全面培训，使其掌握本省所有相关知识。唯有完成此流程，“海南国际呼叫中心”才能正式投入运营，解答商业法规、投资流程、签证手续及旅游咨询等各类问题。由于员工每日仅能工作 8 小时，需组建三支团队实现 24 小时轮班制。倘若存在一种简洁方案能实现上述目标，且操作得当可成为塑造海南品牌的终极“Wow”要素呢？海南需要一位生成式人工智能大使担任信息代理。

生成式 AI 技术已发展到单一 AI 代理可全天候支持多语言服务，同时处理数百次独特交互的水平。它们能解答问题、充当资源库，并作为联络代理处理更复杂的咨询。该 AI 代理永不疲倦地全天候运作，可配置语言自动识别模式，无需语言专家支持。未来众多旅游目的地或将效仿此举，但若海南率先实施，便能掌握先发优势，为品牌建设奠定深远基础。我们拥

有海南长臂猿吉祥物 kiki 这一独特形象，可将其打造为人工智能形象。若能通过高校将该项目开发局限在海南境内，将产生积极影响——这能为海南特定人工智能产业的发展提供“跳板式”助力。若需快速落地，海外已有成熟企业可运用顶尖技术开发符合海南规格要求的人工智能形象。

图 16: 奇奇, 海南长臂猿角色

资料来源: 海南大学-亚利桑那州立大学国际学院纪念品团队、学生创业与创新中心

8. 结论

机遇正向海南招手。这片土地在中国拥有独特优势，足以引领全新发展模式。若说制造业、基础设施建设和房地产曾是中国过去五十年经济繁荣的引擎，那么海南的创新、开放与改革举措，将成为未来五十年全国经济再创辉煌的蓝图。海南既肩负重大责任，亦拥有非凡机遇。本次海南品牌建设研究为该省指明了战略路径。海南品牌建设绝非营销活动，它将推动海南全局层面的战略决策与规划，这使得品牌创建与战略实施的任务更为艰巨。

“海南，自然属于你 (Hainan, Naturally Yours)”、“通往中国的门户 (Your Gateway to and from China)”、“体验自然 (Experience Nature)”这三组主副品牌标语，精准突显了海南的独特优势，既捕捉了海南蕴藏的机遇，也揭示了海南亟待克服的挑战。

9. 附录：品牌成功案例：美国德克萨斯州布莱恩市

9.1. 一座德克萨斯州小城寻找自我定位

根据美国人口普查数据，截至 2020 年，布莱恩市约有 83,980 名居民。这座城市坐落于“德州三角区”核心地带，驱车三小时即可抵达达拉斯、休斯顿和奥斯汀。长期以来，布莱恩始终处于邻近城市大学城的阴影之下——后者是德州农工大学的所在地。这座城市始终努力建立自身独特的旅游目的地形象。

2020 年 7 月，布莱恩市成立非营利性目的地营销组织“目的地布莱恩”，其明确使命是“通过激励人们在德克萨斯州布莱恩市消费时间与金钱来增强社区凝聚力”（图 17）。尽管作为小型乡村社区难免存在局限，但布莱恩的故事之所以引人入胜，并非在于它蜕变为旅游巨头，而在于它找到了兼顾居民与游客需求的可持续模式。

通过他们的努力，布莱恩取得了显著成就：在 2022 年德克萨斯州目的地卓越奖评选中荣获年度最佳目的地营销组织奖，酒店收入创下历史新高，酒店入住率达到十年来的峰值，同时成功保留了其独特的小镇风貌。

图 17：布莱恩目的地标志和团队成员

来源：<https://www.destinationbryan.com/about/>

9.2. 布莱恩的成功秘诀

9.2.1. 真实的品牌标识：“布莱恩传奇”

布莱恩市并未聚焦于建造旅游景点或配套设施以与大型目的地竞争，而是选择以真实性为竞争核心。其核心品牌理念是“A Legend Reborn”，诠释着这样的理念：“布莱恩诞生于多元文化的交汇，植根于深厚的德州传统，是一个充满真实故事、真实人物和真实场所的社区——我们的传奇。我们的传奇在传承德州精神的底色中不断演进。”这一定位精准突显了城市的核心资产：真实的人与真实的故事。

实际上，这是一个发掘本地企业主及其独特家族传承故事的项目，并授予他们“布莱恩传奇”称号：凯尔之家与礼仪咖啡烘焙坊（真正友好的咖啡，在传奇场所烘焙与供应）、卡塔莱纳制帽坊（卡塔莱纳家族打造的德州顶级定制帽饰）、新奥尔良余韵（布拉索斯河谷腹地的地道卡津风味）、浪人农场餐厅（坐落于翻新历史冰库的农场直送餐厅）、采特曼杂货店（采特曼家族传承数代的本地熟食店）、皇后剧院（修复后的布莱恩市中心标志性建筑）、梅西纳霍夫酒庄（历史悠久的本地酒庄）、普布拉纳墨西哥卷饼店（德州著名烤肉卷饼名店）、米尔顿帕克庄园民宿（百年古宅改造的精致民宿）。

图 18: 布莱恩传奇视频

来源: <https://www.youtube.com/@destinationbryan6316/playlists>

9.2.2. 社区参与: 大使计划

布莱恩市推广的一项战略性和创造性举措是其“大使计划”。该计划培训居民和企业主，让他们热情接待游客，并分享小镇的历史和当地企业的故事，包括布莱恩传奇。任何有兴趣成为大使的人都可以参加培训计划，并获得大使徽章认证（见图 19）。“Destination Bryan”项目的目标是尽可能多地认证居民为大使。该项目具有多种功能：

- 对于访客：与居民进行真实、深入的互动，从而提升访客满意度
- 对于居民：了解他们可能不知道的本地服务项目
- 对于企业而言：拓展人脉和交叉推广机会
- 对于 DMO 而言：接收来自基层的反馈意见，并将其纳入旅游战略。

图 19: 大使证书和培训计划

图片来源: 作者照片

9.2.3. 活动策略：创建和增强

Destination Bryan 采用双重活动策略。该机构不仅打造标志性活动，更致力于提升对居民意义重大的社区庆典。目的地布莱恩自主开发的新活动已成为布莱恩城市形象的代名词。然而该机构并不视独立组织的活动为竞争对手，反而积极与其合作，视其为布莱恩最宝贵的资源，并自然承担管理职能以强化既有传统。

“First Friday”是重要现有活动之一。每月首个周五，布莱恩市中心便会化身艺术盛宴：现场音乐、艺术演示、本地商贩与互动活动交相辉映（图 4）。这项已举办二十载的活动已成为区域传统，邻近的德州农工大学校区提供免费接驳车，让参与者轻松抵达。目的地布莱恩通过物资供应与行政支持提升活动品质，彰显其对社区的真诚承诺，赢得了居民的鼎力支持。

图 20：首个周五活动

来源：<https://www.destinationbryan.com/firstfriday/activities/>

最重要的是，布莱恩旅游局每年支持超过 30 项社区活动，这表明其活动策略并非着眼于单一的旗舰节庆活动，而是致力于创造持续不断的旅游和庆祝活动，吸引人们前来体验。以下列举了部分已创建的特色活动以及升级改造的现有活动：

值得探访与庆祝的理由。以下精选了新创的特色活动与升级的现有活动：

全新打造的标志性活动：

- 亮灯时刻！——年度节日开幕盛典，社区居民齐聚主街与布莱恩大道，共同倒数数千盏灯饰的亮灯时刻。
- 喧闹音乐节——劳动节周末举办的多场地、多流派音乐盛会。
- 布莱恩市中心街艺市集——本地艺术家将历史悠久的布莱恩市中心装点得生机盎然，现场设有互动艺术演示、琳琅满目的艺术品展销、现场表演等丰富活动。

现有活动升级：

- 首周五活动——每月举办的市中心主题盛会，呈现现场音乐、艺术演示、本地商贩及互动体验。
- 布拉索斯谷博览会暨牛仔竞技表演——传统德州博览会文化。
- 梅西纳霍夫丰收节——德克萨斯州著名酒庄举办的葡萄酒之乡庆典。

9.2.4. 数字互动：探险护照系统

目的地布莱恩深谙当代游客偏爱互动式移动体验。有别于传统网站或宣传册的景点罗列，该项目推出数字护照计划，将探索之旅转化为趣味游戏。

首个且最成功的项目是布莱恩塔可之旅。该项目汇集全市 44 家地道墨西哥卷饼店、墨西哥餐厅及创意塔可品牌，从加油站附设的传统卷饼摊到市中心时尚融合餐厅一应俱全。此举有效引导游客走出常规景点，深入探索原本难以发现的本土社区。护照系统的理念简单而高效：

- 1) 游客通过智能手机免费注册电子护照。
- 2) 在参与活动的餐厅用餐时，顾客通过应用程序“签到”。
- 3) 签到可累积积分兑换专属奖品。
- 4) 完成全部 44 个站点可获得“布莱恩塔可之旅冠军”旗帜，并在虚拟荣誉墙上永久留名。

继 Taco Trail 取得成功之后，Destination Bryan 又创建了两个数字化互动项目：“Aggieland Art Trail”⁵和“Bryan, Texas History Tour”⁶。

图 21：数字参与计划

来源：布莱恩目的地网站

9.2.5. 战略基础设施：体育旅游投资

布莱恩当地深谙实体基础设施对城镇长期发展的重要性。2022 年 12 月开业的传奇活动中心，正是与布莱恩市政府携手进行战略性基础设施投资，从而提升目的地营销成效的典范。传奇活动中心，是一座占地逾 11,100 平方米的多功能体育娱乐综合体，配备：1) 16 个排球场；2) 8 个篮球场；3) 4 个 NCAA 认证沙滩排球场、4) 6000 平方米特种活动场地、5) 230 平方米室内人工草坪区、6) 510 平方米宴会厅、7) 游戏竞技场及电子竞技休闲区等设施。

该设施将体育旅游定位为城镇的长期经济引擎，而非一次性投资项目。

⁵<https://www.destinationbryan.com/things-to-do/arts-culture-history/art-trail/>

⁶<https://www.destinationbryan.com/history/>

图 22: 传奇活动中心

来源: <https://www.sportsdestinations.com/spotlights/texas/legends-event-center-texas-ultimate-sports-and-33603>

9.3. 布莱恩的成功秘诀

布莱恩旅游目的地项目证明，即使资源有限，小城市也能在不失去自身独特魅力的前提下，实现卓有成效的旅游和品牌建设。通过聚焦真实的本地故事、鼓励居民积极参与、策略性地管理各类活动、充分利用数字化工具以及开展基础设施建设合作，布莱恩从一个被邻近城市光芒掩盖的小城，蜕变为一个惠及游客和当地社区的知名旅游目的地。

布莱恩目的地 (Destination Bryan) 的经验表明，目的地寻求可持续成功的一个可复制公式是：真实身份 + 社区所有权 + 战略活动 + 数字工具 + 基础设施合作 = 可持续的目的地成功 (见表 1)。

表格 1: 布莱恩的成功秘诀

Component	Key Principles
Authentic Identity	Build a brand around genuine local stories; focus on unique strengths rather than competing on weaknesses.
Community Ownership	Ambassador programs turn residents into advocates, benefiting both locals and visitors.
Strategic Events	Create signature events while enhancing existing community celebrations.
Digital Tools	Guide visitor behavior toward local businesses through gamification and data collection.
Infrastructure Partnership	Align marketing with physical development to ensure long-term growth.

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